

A CASE STUDY ON THE TEACHING STRATEGIES OF TEACHERS TEACHING STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL NEEDS

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A Case Study on the Teaching Strategies of Teachers Teaching Students with Special Educational Needs

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Abstract

This single case study aimed to explore the unique teaching styles and strategies of the teachers teaching students with special educational needs, particularly those with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). The researcher also identified the lived experiences and coping mechanisms and insights of the teachers with an autism student. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, three teachers with an autism student were identified. The participants participated in the in-depth interviews. Based on the findings, the researcher found the unique teaching styles and strategies of the teachers in teaching students with autism, including: individualized instruction, manipulative objects, balancing technology and traditional approaches, positive reinforcement, and cultivating a sense of belonging. Based on the findings of the researcher, the researcher found that the challenges and difficulties teachers face in dealing with students with autism are: behavior management, lack of student participation, lack of training, and lack of support. In response to how the participants overcame the challenges and difficulties, the following themes were extracted: managing stress and frustration, collaboration with other educators, relying on family as a support system, and clear communication and simplified language. Upon reflecting on their challenges and difficulties, they arrived at the following insights: individualized learning and learning style, inclusive and supportive classroom environment, challenging stigma and promoting acceptance, and involvement of school psychologists and training for mainstream teachers.

Keywords: *teaching strategies, teaching styles, teachers, students, special educational needs, Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)*

Introduction

Students with special educational needs have long been a significant concern in general education settings. These students have the right to access all learning resources and participate in group activities within a typical classroom environment. Studies show teachers express a desire to include students with special educational needs in their classrooms. However, they often lack the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively address the educational demands of these students. This highlights the need for better teacher training and teaching strategies and access to information on creating inclusive and effective learning environments (Subarna et al., 2022).

In India, the main issue lies in the application of theoretical knowledge about special educational needs into practical teaching strategies. Teachers often struggle to translate their understanding into effective classroom methods, leading to a lack of empathy and understanding for students with special needs. The absence of appropriate strategies means these students may not receive the necessary individualized attention, leading to feelings of isolation and academic stagnation. The situation is further complicated by an over-reliance on traditional teaching methods, which are often unsuitable for students with educational needs. The root of the problem is the lack and the absence of effective teaching strategies for special needs students. (Gorai et al., 2021).

Moreover, in Isabela, Philippines, specifically in the City Division of Ilagan, many teachers lack effective strategies for teaching students with special needs. They often feel unprepared due to a lack of updated teaching guides, curriculum guides, and seminars. This has led to challenges in providing quality education for these students. Despite the "Primary Education Development Plan" (PEDP) aiming to improve mainstream education, the quality of primary education, particularly for students with special needs, remains below par in Ilagan City (Allan et al., 2021).

The researcher conducted a study because it was highly relevant to society. There was an urgency to conduct this study as it addressed the pressing need for inclusive and effective teaching strategies in mainstream education. By exploring the practices and challenges in classrooms, it aimed to enhance the quality of education for students with special educational needs, promoting their academic and social development. If this problem was ignored, it would continue to exist and negatively affect the quality of learning for students, especially those with special educational needs. Therefore, the study, by exploring teaching strategies and challenges, aimed to enhance education quality, inform policy-making, and foster inclusivity. It aligned with global efforts for equal education, making it a timely and essential contribution to the educational landscape.

In connection, there are several international studies conducted in relation to teaching strategies for teachers working with students with special educational needs, including the studies of Subarna et al., (2022), titled "Teaching Strategies for Students with Disabilities in Regular Classes," Hazmi et al., (2018), titled "Universal Design for Learning to Support Access to the General Education Curriculum for Students with Intellectual Disabilities" and Chiwandire et al., (2019) "Funding And Inclusion In Higher Education Institutions For Students With Special Educational Needs". They gave us useful ideas on how to teach students with special educational needs better.

These studies collectively provide valuable insights into effective teaching approaches for individuals with special educational needs. My research provides a unique blend of specialization and in-depth analysis of teaching strategies within the context of a case study. This holistic approach contributes significantly to the field of special education, enhancing our understanding of how to support and educate students with special educational needs.

Copies of the study will be disseminated to a variety of research conferences. This will also be published in a reputable internationally indexed journal. The intent behind this initiative was to foster an environment of academic exchange and to leverage the findings derived from the research. By doing so, the aim was to enhance knowledge and facilitate its application in relevant fields of work and study.

Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following questions related to the teaching strategies used by teachers teaching students with special educational needs:

1. What are the unique teaching styles and strategies of the teachers teaching students with special educational needs?
2. What are the lived experiences of teachers when utilizing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs in a classroom?
3. How did the teachers cope with the challenges faced in implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs?
4. What are the insights of the teachers' teaching students with special educational needs when using different strategies to cater the needs of the students?

Methodology

Research Design

The methodology used in this study adopted a qualitative research design, specifically employing a case study approach. The aim was to comprehensively investigate and dive into the characteristics and features of various causes related to teaching strategies employed by educators working with students with special educational needs. According to Rashid et al. (2019), qualitative case studies offered a descriptive analysis of a particular occurrence in a particular setting. Additionally, this study design exhibited a procedural endeavor to gather information about the phenomenon through interviews and interactive conversations in order to understand the teaching styles, experiences, viewpoints, insights, and observable specific circumstances (Aspers & Corte, 2019).

The best approach used in this study was a qualitative research design. This method was crucial for conducting in-depth inquiries into how the teachers perceived and engaged with a specific phenomenon within its general context. By using this strategy, the study was able to collect crucial data that aided in understanding the teaching strategies teachers used in teaching students with educational needs. By conducting interviews, describing the experiences, difficulties, and insights of the informants of the specific study, and then analyzing the data, a qualitative design was used to explore and comprehend the unique case, statements, and insights of the informants.

The qualitative study utilized a case study. As per Lune and Berg (2017), qualitative research pertained to the endeavor of the researcher to understand the situation and its uniqueness, in relation to its context and the interactions inscribed herein. Moreover, this research design was described as an investigation of things in their natural settings. It was also added that such was an attempt made by the researcher to interpret or make sense of a phenomenon taken from the raw perspectives of the people involved in the said event.

In this study, a case study approach was used, which was ideal for this research. This method involved studying situations in their natural settings. The researcher tried to understand a phenomenon from the viewpoints of those involved. Specifically, the study examined the teaching strategies used by educators for students with special educational needs, specifically those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). The case study approach allowed for a detailed look at these strategies in a real-world context, offering valuable insights into their effectiveness and how they influenced student learning.

Participants

The primary participants in this study were the teachers of Magatos Integrated School in Magatos, Asuncion, teaching students with special educational needs, specifically Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Additionally, one informant was interviewed for each participant to support their unique responses to the research questions. These informants included co-teachers and a parent. The selection of participants was justified as the study targeted teachers instructing students with special educational needs in a mainstream environment, making them the most suitable sources for providing authentic insights on the research topic. Following the study criteria, three participants were selected. The researcher conducted thorough interviews with all three individuals, engaging in one-on-one sessions with each participant and their respective informant.

This number was chosen in accordance with following Dornyei (2007), which stated that two (2) to twelve (12) research participants were enough to reach saturation in a case study.

The criteria specified by the researcher are appropriate for the study. The following criteria are used in choosing the participants: firstly,

participants had to be teachers who held a Bachelor's degree in Elementary Education. Secondly, they should have had a minimum of ten years of teaching experience. Lastly, participants had to have a student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in their mainstream classroom.

This study employed a case study approach, involving three distinct cases to gather diverse perspectives on the experiences of educators and parents of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Case 1 focused on the experiences of one educator who taught students with ASD in a regular classroom setting, supplemented by the insights of one parent of a student with autism. Case 2 involved one educator and one co-teacher, while Case 3 included one educator and one co-teacher. These participants were carefully selected to ensure a range of perspectives and experiences, enriching the study's findings.

Procedure

As a researcher, it was my responsibility to ensure that all prospective participants fully understood the nature of my research study before they decided to take part. To maintain the integrity of the research process and recruitment, I administered consent and agreement forms prior to conducting interviews. These forms provided participants with the opportunity to review the terms and conditions, ensuring that their involvement was entirely voluntary and a crucial contributor to the research's success.

The researcher followed a structured protocol throughout the study, encompassing every phase from pre-interview preparations to post-interview procedures. Initially, a set of interview guide questions was prepared, which was subsequently subjected to validation by a panel of validators. Following this, an endorsement letter was obtained, and to proceed with the study under the endorsement, approval was sought from the advisor. Subsequently, approval was sought from the research office and a formal letter was obtained authorizing the researcher to conduct face-to-face interviews.

After receiving the necessary approvals, letters were obtained for the selected participants, formally requesting their consent to partake in this study. If the chosen participants agreed to participate, they were supplied with a consent form for their signature. Subsequently, upon obtaining the approval letter from the validation panel, the study was initiated. Prior to conducting the interviews, an orientation session was conducted by the researcher for all participants. During this session, the purpose, methodology, and the rights of the participants in the interview process were elucidated. Additionally, permission to record the entire interview duration was sought from the participants. Following the interviews, measures were taken to safeguard the confidentiality of all recorded sessions. The recorded data was transcribed, and the resulting transcripts were subjected to verification by the participants. Upon completion of the verification process, the data was translated and analyzed. The findings derived from this data analysis were then utilized to formulate conclusions and offer recommendations based on the study's outcome.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the in-depth interviews were transcribed, translated, and analyzed following the process proposed by Creswell (2009) for data analysis. The researcher followed the recommended steps outlined by Creswell.

The translated responses of the participants were coded to create a thematic analysis of the data for this case study. Thematic analysis, also known as coding, involved categorizing responses and identifying recurring themes in the text. This process helped develop a structured representation of thematic ideas, providing valuable insights into the data that could be further analyzed and measured.

Through the systematic process of thematic analysis, the researcher organized the dataset into themes or patterns. This allowed the researcher to identify and develop themes based on the obtained data, as described by Dye (2021).

During the data analysis phase, the researcher relied on the transcripts and translations of the informants' responses. By using the coding process, the researcher grouped and organized the repeated responses to generate a comprehensive theme analysis. The concepts were sorted and evaluated based on their relationships, similarities, and contrasts, with the assistance of a data analyst. This rigorous coding and thematic analysis approach ensured a thorough examination of the data and helped uncover meaningful patterns and insights.

Ethical Considerations

In this study, the primary focus was on teachers in the field of education, with a secondary emphasis on educators in general. Ensuring the safety and security of these participants was of utmost importance to maintain their trust and confidence in the research process. The researcher upheld ethical principles, including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent, and confidentiality, as outlined by Boyatzis (1998) and Mack et al. (2005).

These principles guided the researcher in conducting the study with integrity, respecting the rights and well-being of the participants, and maintaining the confidentiality of their information. By adhering to these ethical principles, the researcher aimed to create a safe and trustworthy environment for the participants, fostering a positive research experience and contributing to the overall validity and reliability of the study.

Respect for persons encompassed recognizing their dignity, which granted them the authority to make claims and demands that limited the actions of others. As Darwall (2004) suggested, dignity provided reasons for individuals to comply with these claims and demands, ensuring that their autonomy and rights were respected.

This underscored the responsibility of the researcher to consider the vulnerabilities of the research participants. To avoid the development of undue familiarity, all interactions were approached with a sense of professionalism and self-sufficiency. Furthermore, prior to conducting interviews, permission was sought from both school administrators and participants, and interview schedules were thoughtfully arranged to minimize disruption to classes and other commitments.

Benevolence emphasized that participants should prioritize reducing their potential risks rather than maximizing financial gains. Ensuring the interviewees' anonymity was essential to safeguard participants from potential harm. To protect their identities, pseudonyms were used, ensuring that the information shared remained confidential (Bricki & Green, 2007).

The researcher maintained the interviewees' anonymity by using pseudonyms or fictitious names when referring to them in any documentation or reporting of the study. By adopting this approach, the researcher could ensure that the information shared remained confidential and that the participants' identities were not revealed to anyone outside of the researcher. This practice helped create a secure and trustworthy environment for the participants, promoting their willingness to share their experiences and insights openly and honestly.

Consent was a vital aspect of showing respect for research participants. It involved making sure all participants fully understood the research goals and objectives. Written permission was obtained to secure their approval. Participants enthusiastically engaged in in-depth interviews after receiving a positive response. They were later informed of the study's findings and results, maintaining transparency and respect for their involvement (Creswell, 2012).

In this research, participants were provided with informed consent forms before the in-depth interviews. They had the flexibility to select suitable interview times and locations that enabled them to express their thoughts and insights freely. Following their agreement and the completion of interviews, three participants in in-depth interviews (IDI) were informed of the study's results.

Confidentiality regarding the results and findings, including the safety of all the data and the participants, a coding system and pseudonyms were employed to conceal the identities of the participants. Additionally, all research materials, such as encoded transcripts and notes containing sensitive information, were securely disposed of after data processing (Maree, 2007).

During interviews, participant hesitations were addressed sensitively, emphasizing the confidentiality of their responses. It was important to ensure that participants volunteered their information without coercion, in line with the principles of data privacy under the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Justice required reasonable allocation of the risks and benefits as the results of the study. Therefore, acknowledging the contribution of all the participants was highlighted as they became an integral part of the success of this study. They were given due credit in all their endeavors (Bloom & Crabtree, 2006).

In the context of this study, justice was upheld through the fair distribution of risks and benefits among participants. Recognizing the pivotal role of all contributors was crucial as they significantly influenced the study's success. Each participant received proper acknowledgment and credit for their efforts, underscoring their integral part in the research outcomes. Additionally, to ensure a positive experience and show appreciation, participants were provided with support during interviews, including snacks and thoughtful tokens as gestures of gratitude. This approach aimed to maintain a positive reputation and foster goodwill among participants throughout the study.

Results and Discussion

Participants

All three (3) participants in the study were teachers with a Bachelor's degree in Elementary Education and at least 10 years of teaching experience. Currently, they were employed as educators at Magatos Integrated School, where they were responsible for teaching a student who has Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in a mainstream classroom setting. Each participant also had an informant to support their assertions. A total of three informants were involved to offer responses to specific questions that the study sought to explore. The subjects consisted of six females aged between 40 and 55, as indicated in Table 1 of this chapter.

The participants of the study satisfied the predetermined criteria set for the research, guaranteeing that they have the necessary knowledge and expertise to offer important insights. Their extensive knowledge and direct involvement as educators in a mainstream classroom setting, dealing with a student who has been diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), greatly enhanced their contribution to the research. By relying on their knowledge and experiences, the study hopes to develop a thorough understanding of the obstacles and effective solutions for educating students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

The in-depth interviews were carried out in person on the premises of Magatos Integrated School. The researcher approached the participants and inquired about their willingness to participate in an interview. Although the majority of participants were in agreement, there was one participant who was preoccupied and unable to take part. As a response, the researcher successfully recruited another volunteer who was available and willing to participate in the interview. Both the interviewer and interviewees mutually adjusted their schedules to make the interview possible.

During the interviews, the researcher and participants communicated effectively and clearly. The participants were free to reject to answer any question they thought unhelpful or contradictory to their wishes. To maintain confidentiality, the information and data gathered during the interviews were treated with strict confidentiality. Only the researcher and the participants had access to this information, which was shared verbally but not included in the study due to its sensitive nature.

In order to verify compliance with the data collection procedure, the researcher employed smartphones to document the participants' responses during the interviews. Before commencing the recording, the researcher obtained consent from all participants to capture the full conversation, and all individuals gladly accepted. The research participants shown understanding and accommodation in response to this request, acknowledging the significance of upholding confidentiality.

In order to protect the identities of all the participants, pseudonyms were assigned to each participant. In this case, pseudonyms were also given to ensure the anonymity of the participants. "Abacus" is not the participant's real name; it was chosen because during the interview, she expressed her desire to have an abacus in her classroom to teach numeracy skills. She had been requesting an abacus from the school for a long time, but it had not been provided yet. "Violet" is not the informant's real name; it was chosen because she was wearing a violet shirt during the interview. "Artist" is another pseudonym used for a participant who shared during the interview that teachers sometimes need to adapt to the students' behavior and go with the flow. Additionally, the researcher was captivated by her physical appearance. "Bubble" is not her real name. The researcher gave this name to this informant because her personality is bubbly. "Extraordinary" for her innovative approaches to enhancing classroom participation and student learning. She created an engaging classroom environment by including visual aids, interactive activities, and individualized learning plans to meet the unique needs of her students on the autism spectrum. "Star" is a pseudonym of the informant. The researcher gave this name to the informant because during the interview she possesses a kind attitude and is hopeful to the future generation. These pseudonyms were used to ensure the confidentiality and privacy of the participants.

Categorization of Data

After conducting the interviews, the recorded conversations were transcribed, translated, and subsequently analyzed. The analysis process began with coding, which involved organizing the data into meaningful segments. This coding technique helped create a description of the participants and the categories of themes to be analyzed. These themes were then used to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomena being investigated.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

	<i>Pseudonym</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Teaching Grade</i>	<i>Function</i>	<i>Code</i>
Case 1	Abacus	52	Female	Kindergarten	Participant	IDI-01
– Teaching Strategies of Teachers	Violet	55	Female		Informant	IDI-02
Teaching Students with Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD)	Artist	40	Female	Grade VI	Participant	IDI-03
	Bubble	42	Female	Grade V	Informant	IDI-04
	Extraordinary	43	Female	Grade I	Participant	IDI-05
	Star	45	Female	Grade III	Informant	IDI-06

To further classify the data, major themes were identified to address each research question. These themes were thoroughly discussed and elaborated upon to provide a detailed overview and description. Finally, the researcher reached conclusions and verified the initial concepts and patterns found in the data.

To ensure the trustworthiness of the study, the researcher paid attention to the dimensions of credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. To address credibility, member certification was conducted, along with the triangulation approach. This involved providing the participants with copies of the interview transcripts for their review and certification of authenticity. The participants provided their signatures on the participant verification form to indicate their agreement with the content.

To ensure dependability and confirmability, the researcher took measures to maintain the integrity of the study. An audit record of the participants' responses was kept, documenting the entire process from transcription to verification. This record ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the participants' information. Transcription, verification, and triangulation were employed as methods to validate the results, assumptions, and conjectures in the study. These processes contributed to the dependability and confirmability of the study by ensuring that the data collected and analyzed were trustworthy and aligned with the participants' perspectives and experiences.

In terms of transferability, the researcher acknowledges the importance of allowing readers to determine the applicability of the study's findings to their own situations (Polit & Beck, 2014). Transferability refers to the potential for the results of the study to be relevant or adaptable to different contexts or environments. By providing a thorough description of the research methodology, data analysis process, and findings, other researchers can assess the transferability of the findings to their own settings.

ABACUS

This case involved one participant and one informant, both of whom were female. The participant was a Master Teacher I with at least 10 years of teaching experience. She had a student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in her mainstream classroom, while the informant was the parent of the student. Abacus (pseudonym) demonstrates a deep understanding of the complex behavioral patterns

and learning challenges specific to a student with ASD. Students with ASD often face common difficulties, including challenges with social interactions, communication barriers, sensory sensitivities, repetitive behaviors, and difficulties with transitions or changes in routine. These learning challenges can impact various aspects of education, including academic performance, social skills development, and overall classroom participation. Abacus's tailored teaching methods, emphasizing hands-on, multisensory activities, and the supportive classroom environment she creates, characterized by emotional encouragement and positive reinforcement, provide a safe space for the student's self-expression and development. Through the strategic use of visual aids and manipulative objects, Abacus enriches the student's educational experience, aiming to nurture a sense of accomplishment and pride through personalized positive reinforcement.

The insights shared by both the teacher and the student's parent offer valuable perspectives on the specialized approaches essential for effectively supporting the learning and growth of students with ASD. This collaboration between the teacher and parent provides a holistic view of the student's needs and challenges, highlighting the importance of tailored interventions and a nurturing educational environment.

Research Question No. 1: What are the unique teaching styles and strategies of the teachers teaching students with special educational needs?

This question study sought to discover the unique teaching styles and strategies employed by the teacher when working with a student with special educational needs, particularly Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). This involved tailoring methods to the student's distinct behaviors and needs, such as adjusting seating arrangements and providing personalized activities. The teacher also focused on fostering a supportive and accepting classroom atmosphere, demonstrating patience and persistence to guide the student through tasks. In the responses of the two participants, there were six emerging themes that the researcher had found. The following themes are: individualized approach, emotional support and nurturing environment, visual learning and memory enhancement, hands-on learning and creative expression, limited technological enhancement, encouragement and motivation.

Individualized Approach

The participant emphasized prioritizing hands-on, multisensory activities to address the student's specific learning requirements, focusing on developing fundamental skills such as name recognition and hand-eye coordination. The teacher's distinct method revolved around catering to the unique needs of the student with ASD and fostering inclusivity within the traditional classroom environment.

Abacus (pseudonym) highlighted her use of personalized teaching strategies to cater to the unique needs of the student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), ensuring customized instruction for the best possible learning results. Her approach focused on individualized attention and tailored instruction, aiming to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment. She stated:

“Gina lahi gyud na siya, lahi iyang activity, mag one-on-one mi ana sa table.” (IDI-01)

(He is really different. His activities are unique, and I engage with him one-on-one at the table.)

Furthermore, Violet (pseudonym) echoes Abacus (pseudonym)'s assessment of her child's distinctive activities and commends the teacher's adept instructional techniques that are customized to address the student's individual requirements. She expressed her appreciation for the teacher's effective approach in adapting instruction to suit her child's needs, emphasizing the positive impact of tailored teaching methods on her child's learning experience. She said:

“Makita nako nga lahi ang mga activities ni (name of the student) ug kanang gina lahi siya ni ma'am, usahay gali kay ginahatagan ni ma'am ug activity na sa balay buhaton.” (IDI-02)

(I can see that (name of the student) engages in different activities, sometimes, provides her with activities to do at home.)

Emotional Support and Nurturing Environment

By providing comfort, care, and positive reinforcement, educators aim to cultivate an environment that fosters a sense of security and empowerment for students with autism. Ultimately, the focus is on creating a nurturing environment that values each student's unique needs and encourages their emotional development alongside academic progress.

During the in-depth interview, Abacus (pseudonym) emphasized the significance of creating an emotional support and nurturing environment in the classroom for students with special educational needs. By providing comfort, demonstrating care, and employing positive affirmations, teachers can cultivate a secure and encouraging space where students feel valued, understood, and empowered to express themselves. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“Mag answer pud siya diha sa among activity ako pud gunitan iyang kamot. Ipakita nako sa ilaha nga motherly gyud nako sa ilaha niya mag hilak2 na siya I love nako “love2 maam bi” “ayaw na hilak kay mo balik man si mama unya.” (IDI-01)

(He participates in our activity, and I help him with his work. I show everyone that I'm very motherly towards them. Sometimes he cries, and I tell him, "I love you." "Don't cry because your mom will be back soon.")

Furthermore, Violet (pseudonym) expressed that being a mother to a child with Autism presents challenges, but she acknowledges that

Abacus (pseudonym) is dedicated to providing a supportive learning experience for her child. Her words highlight the crucial role of educators in fostering a supportive and enriching educational journey for students with special needs. She said:

“Lisod mahimong inahan sa usa ka bata nga naay Autism apan nakita jud nako nga maayo nga maistra si ma’am kay kanang... gina suportahan ug gina tudloan ra gyud gihapon niya akong anak. (IDI-02)

(It is difficult being a mother to a child with Autism, but I truly see Ma'am as a good teacher because she supports and teaches my child consistently.)

Visual Learning and Memory Enhancement

Visual aids, such as charts, graphs, diagrams, maps, photographs, illustrations, videos, and interactive multimedia presentations and pictures offer crucial support for students with autism who encounter challenges in reading, significantly boosting their learning outcomes and memory retention. These visual representations not only aid in understanding but also play a crucial role in improving memory retrieval, exemplifying the effectiveness of visual learning strategies tailored for students with autism.

The emphasis on the importance of visual aids, like pictures, for autism students who are not yet proficient in reading suggests a focus on enhancing learning through visual cues and memory retention. The use of images to aid in comprehension and memory recall, highlights the significance of visual learning strategies in early education. Abacus (pseudonym) revealed that:

“Pag maka kita na sila ug picture ilaha na dayun ng litokon pero kuhaa ang picture dili na sila kabalo. Kinahanglan jud sila ug picture, kung wala koy picture no, mag drawing na lang ko ana. Imaginon na na nila so remembering ma apply na nako sa ilaha.” (IDI-01)

(When they see a picture, they understand it immediately, but if the picture is removed, they no longer recognize it. They really need pictures. If I do not have a picture, I just draw it. They can imagine it. This way, I can help them remember.)

Hands-On Learning and Creative Expression

It involves interactive educational activities that encourage physical engagement and creativity, promoting experiential learning. This approach enhances understanding, retention, and student engagement by allowing them to actively participate in the learning process. Through creative expression, students can showcase their individual perspectives using various mediums like art, music, and hands-on projects.

The use of manipulative toys and colorful blocks provides children with tangible experiences that enhance their cognitive and physical development. By engaging in activities that involve building and creating with blocks, children not only develop fine motor skills but also exercise their imagination and problem-solving abilities. Abacus (pseudonym) emphasizes:

“Kinahanglan na lang ana nila dapat no kanang mag form kanang mga dulaan bitaw mga manipulative toys, hatagan na siya ug mga colorful nga mga block blocks ba sige, I porma na dinha bisan unsa imong porma kay atong picturan ganahan ka mo porma ana kay ato iyaha ra manang ana anaon patong patongon.” (IDI-01)

(They should have manipulative toys to form different shapes - colorful blocks, for example. You can form anything you want there, and we will take a picture. You enjoy shaping it because you are the one who will shape it, and then we will stack them up.)

Limited Technological Enhancement

Limited Technological Enhancement refers to the deliberate restriction or controlled use of advanced technological tools and resources in educational settings. This approach involves utilizing technology sparingly to prevent overreliance and maintain a balance between traditional teaching methods and digital integration. By limiting technological enhancements, educators aim to prioritize human interaction, critical thinking, and hands-on learning experiences.

In the interview, it was mentioned by Abacus (pseudonym) that they primarily use a TV via a laptop for classes, incorporating semi-PowerPoint presentations along with a mix of flashcards and storytelling through videos. However, the technology's impact on enhancing learning is limited. She stated:

“naga gamit sila ug tv lang through kini bitawng through laptop na ilang mga klase semi power point gihapon pero kanang mix na kung unsa lang tong letter kato ra pud ilang I flash ing-ana ba unya pagka human mag story telling sila so syempre mag gamit sila laptop kanang mga videos lang. About anang technology nga ginagamit dili kaayo sila 50% jud nga mo enhance diha kay assisted pa man sila nako.” (IDI-01)

(They only use TV through a laptop for their classes, still with semi-PowerPoint presentations, but only a mix of whatever letters are flashed. When it comes to storytelling, they are naturally used to the laptop for videos. In terms of the technology used, it does not really enhance much, as they will still have assisted by me, less than 50% improvement is observation.)

Encouragement and Motivation

Encouragement and motivation play a pivotal role for teachers supporting students with Autism in mainstream classrooms, providing

crucial emotional support and empowerment. By offering consistent encouragement, teachers cultivate a sense of confidence, resilience, and self-worth in students with Autism. Motivating students with Autism enhances their engagement, participation, and academic achievements, contributing significantly to their overall personal growth and development within the classroom setting.

Abacus (pseudonym), shared a valuable insight with the researcher. She emphasized the importance of praising students with autism for their hard work as a key strategy for fostering a sense of accomplishment. This approach, according to Abacus, is crucial for cultivating a positive learning environment and promoting self-confidence in students who may face unique challenges in traditional educational settings. She proved it by stating:

“Daygon nako na sila, dili jud na sila pwede dili ko mo dayeg kay kinahanglan na daygon nimo na sila sa ilahang gi buhat. “Very good!”, “palakpakan nato” ana lipay kaayo na sila proud kaayo na sila sa ilahang kaugalingon nga “ay very good diay ko.” (IDI-01)

(I will praise them; they cannot go without me praising them because you need to acknowledge their efforts. "Very good!" "Let us clap" - they are very happy, very proud of their self "oh, I am really good.")

Violet (pseudonym) expressed her gratitude that her son is not being neglected at school. When her son comes home, he excitedly shares that he received a star from his teacher, Abacus (pseudonym). Violet (pseudonym) motivates her son to go in school. Her encouragement and support play a crucial role in inspiring her son to thrive academically and emotionally. She stated:

“Pag mo uli na siya gikan skwelahan mo ingon na siya sa akua nga gi tatakan daw ug stars ang iyahang notebook bisan gud ug wala kaayo nagka dimao kay di pa man gyud kaayo siya kabalo mo sulat pero, akua siya gina ingnan nga “maayo dong, padayon lang sa imong pag skwela.” (IDI-02)

(When he comes home from school, he tells me that his notebook seems to be filled with stars, even though he is not very good at writing yet. I encourage him by saying, 'Good job, keep up the good work in school.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of teachers when utilizing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs in a classroom?

The questions focused on the teachers' experiences when implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs, particularly those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), in a classroom setting. These inquiries aimed to uncover the challenges, struggles, and difficulties encountered by the teachers. From the responses of the two participants, the researcher identified five prominent themes that emerged: communication challenges, lack of participation, importance of regular school attendance, behavioral management, lack of assistance.

Communication Challenges

Through exploring the teaching strategies of teachers working with students with autism, I was struck by the profound communication challenges Abacus (pseudonym) faced, particularly with non-verbal autistic children. My interview with teachers like Abacus, who shared her experiences, revealed the immense difficulty in engaging these students effectively. The absence of verbal communication creates a significant hurdle, requiring teachers to develop alternative ways to understand their needs and thoughts.

In the context of communication challenges with a non-verbal child with autism, it becomes particularly challenging for teachers to engage effectively. This highlights the significant communication hurdles that teachers face when working with non-verbal students, especially those with special needs like Autism Spectrum Disorder. Abacus (pseudonym) stated that:

“Ang lisdan lang gyud nako sa bata kanang dili mo tingog kanang pangutan on, mo tingog na siya sa akua pero hinay kaayo so lisod jud kaayo ug maka studyante ka ug ing-ana.” (IDI-01)

(It is really challenging for me when the child does not speak. Even if they respond to me, it is very soft, so it is really difficult to teach student like that.)

Violet (pseudonym) echoed the ongoing challenge of communicating with her son, who struggles with inconsistent responses, underscoring the continuous effort required to connect effectively. This communication barrier emphasizes the intricate process of understanding his needs and emotions, demanding patience and understanding. She stated:

“Ambot anang bataa sobra gyud ka hilakon mamahon kaayo, maulaw na lang ko kay ma'am kay sige hilak sa classroom maong pagawson na lang na siya usahay. Mo ingon si ma'am nga "didto na lang sa ka sa imong mama kaw, ayaw na hilak ha.” (IDI-02)

(I do not know why that child cries so much, it is really excessive. I'm embarrassed for him because he cries so often in the classroom, so sometimes I just send him out. The teacher would say, 'Just go to your mom, stop crying, okay?)

Lack of Participation

Limited participation in classroom activities is a significant challenge for students with autism, often rooted in underlying literacy difficulties and social communication preferences. As observed by Abacus, students with autism may struggle with basic literacy skills, such as reading or writing their name, and frequently rely on non-verbal communication. Furthermore, some students with autism may

exhibit a reluctance to engage in social interactions with their teacher and classmates. These challenges can significantly impact their developmental progress and hinder their active participation in classroom discussions.

These challenges, as observed by Abacus (pseudonym) can significantly impact a child's ability to engage in academic activities and participate fully in the learning process. The lack of participation can further exacerbate developmental delays, creating a cycle that requires targeted intervention and support. Educators must recognize the unique needs of students with autism and implement strategies that address their literacy and communication challenges to foster a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“Dili man gyud siya makabalo mo basa. Dili siya kabalo mo sulat sa iyang ngalan, unya mag pitok2 lang gyud siya handtod run.” (IDI-01)

(He really cannot read. He does not know how to write his name, and he just blink until now.)

Importance of Regular School Attendance

Regular school attendance is vital for academic success, as it enables students to fully learning, participate in classroom activities, and build relationships with teachers and peers. Frequent absences can lead to missed opportunities for learning, falling behind in studies, and lower academic performance.

Abacus (pseudonym) emphasized the critical role of attendance in teaching students with autism, underscoring that regular participation is essential for facilitating consistent learning progress and fostering a supportive educational environment tailored to their special needs, highlighting the importance of individualized attention and personalized learning strategies to enhance their educational experience effectively. She stated:

“Ayaw sige ug absent kay basin pag abot sa closing maka balo ra ka. Kabalo na man to siya saiyang ngalan uy pero kinahanglan jud lagi nga taga adlaw naa jud ka unya kay absenot man. Kanang attendance, isa gyud ng attendance kinahanglan mo skwela gyud kay ag bata pag sige ug absent wala nay matun-an.” (IDI-01)

(Do not be absent often because by the end of the class, you will know your name. The child already knows his name. But you really need to be present every day because if you keep on being absent, there will be no learning.)

Furthermore, Violet (pseudonym) shared instances where her son lacks enthusiasm for attending school, yet she perseveres in ensuring his attendance even in the face of his reluctance. Her unwavering commitment to prioritizing his education reflects a dedicated effort to provide him with consistent learning opportunities and support. This steadfast approach underscores the importance of parental involvement and advocacy in overcoming challenges and promoting a positive educational experience for children with unique needs. She said:

“usahay man gud ma’am kay di siya ganahan mo skwela kay kapoy daw pero akoa jud siya gina ingnan nga kinahanglan gyud niya mo skwela kay unsaon na lang wa siyay matun-an, basig daog-daogon ra siya puhon.” (IDI-02)

(Sometimes, ma’am, he does not want to go to school because he says it is tiring, but I really tell him that he needs to go to school because otherwise, he would not learn anything, and he might regret it in the future.)

Behavioral Management

Managing the behaviors of students with autism presents significant challenges due to the diverse and often unpredictable nature of their behaviors. The individualized needs and communication differences of students with autism require tailored approaches to address behavioral challenges effectively. Educators and support staff play a crucial role in implementing strategies that promote positive behavior and support the overall well-being of students with autism.

Each day brings a unique mix of students with varying levels of social engagement, ranging from reserved to more prone to emotional outbursts. This dynamic classroom environment can be particularly demanding, requiring educators to navigate individual needs and adapt their teaching strategies to accommodate diverse learning styles and emotional responses. The presence of a student with autism, who may exhibit unique communication and social challenges. Abacus (pseudonym) emphasized:

“Sa teacher man gud kanunay man gyud na ang lisod, taga adlaw naa guyu lahi lahing mga bata nga imohang ma encounter kay ilang mga batasan lahi-lahi man gud nay bata nga saputon karun, naay bata nga sig hilak. Sa akong klase mag hilak2 gali na siya mag lisod na ko, naga klase nako mag ana na siya ipa uban nako siya sa iyang mama, mo hilak mura bitaw ug sa first day sa klase ing ana.” (IDI-01)

(It seems that being a teacher is really challenging, especially when dealing with different kinds of children every day with varying behaviors. Some kids are quiet, while others are more prone to crying. In my class, if he starts crying, I usually comfort them and ask them to join me with their mother. They cry as if it is the first day of class.)

The child's excessive crying poses a significant challenge for the teacher, leading to moments of discomfort and potential distraction to class. In response, the teacher occasionally directs the child to his mother, urging him to stop crying. This, as Violet, the child's

mother, observes, can sometimes feel like a quick fix rather than a genuine attempt to address the underlying cause of the child's distress. This is expressed by Violet (pseudonym):

“Ambot anang bataa sobra gyud ka hilakon mamahon kaayo, maulaw na lang ko kay ma'am kay sige hilak sa classroom maong pagawson na lang na siya usahay. Mo ingon si ma'am nga "didto na lang sa ka sa imong mama kaw, ayaw na hilak ha.” (IDI-02)

(I do not know why that child cries excessively, it is really too much. I feel embarrassed because he cries a lot in the classroom, so I sometimes just let him go outside. The teacher would say, 'Just go to your mom, stop crying, okay?')

Lack of Assistance

The lack of essential resources, such as an abacus, despite repeated requests, highlights the challenges faced by educators in creating inclusive learning environments for students with autism. The disparity in resource allocation between Abacus's setting and a well-equipped SPED program underscores the critical need for equitable access to resources to enhance teaching efficacy and student engagement in mainstream classrooms.

The lack of assistance for teachers, as highlighted by Abacus (pseudonym), is a significant concern impacting their working conditions and job satisfaction. Despite years passing without receiving the desired abacus and rubber mat for tumbling activities, Abacus (pseudonym), remains steadfast in their preference for these resources. The contrast in support between the SPED program, which seems well-equipped with abundant resources, and the limited assistance where Abacus (pseudonym) works, is evident. Observing the colorful materials and attractive resources available to others further emphasizes the disparity in support, underscoring the importance of equitable access to resources for all educators to enhance teaching effectiveness and student engagement. She emphasizes:

“pila na ka tuig ang ni labay wala pa juy ni abot nako diri na kanang abacus, abacus ra gyud ang akong gusto ug rubber mat kay mag tumbling2 biya ning mga bata. Kanang kuan oh SPED oh daghan kaayo na sila ug support gikan sa ilaha kay pagkakita bitaw nako sa iyang mga materials color2 na ilahang table unya naa pa jud na silay mga gwapo na mga materials nga ni abot.” (IDI-01)

(It has been several years, and I still have not received the abacus I have been waiting for here. I really prefer the abacus and a rubber mat for the tumbling activities the children enjoy. It is striking to see the abundant support provided to the SPED program, evident from the colorful materials on their tables and the attractive resources they have.)

Research Question No. 3: How did the teachers cope with the challenges faced in implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs?

In response to the inquiry on how participants deal with the encountered challenges, their coping strategies were subjected to thematic analysis, revealing five significant themes that encapsulate their coping mechanisms. The emerging themes are: stress and anger management, encouraging mastery and independence in learning, curriculum adaptation, familial support and involvement in educational endeavors, and professional development of educators.

Stress and Anger Management

In managing stress and frustration when working with students with autism, it is crucial not to internalize the stress caused by their behavior but rather maintain a patient and understanding approach to their unique challenges. Understanding the child's perspective and individual needs is key to developing appropriate strategies that can effectively support their learning and well-being.

Abacus (pseudonym) emphasizes the significance of avoiding personal frustration and stress while interacting with students with autism, highlighting the importance of staying calm and seeking alternative approaches to address their educational requirements. By focusing on proactive and empathetic responses, educators can create a positive and supportive learning environment that caters to the specific needs of students with autism. She stated:

“dili lang gyud nimo ibutang imong kaugalingon nga ma stress jud ka anang bataa so dili stress imong hunahunaon kundili ang iyahang pamaagi unsa ning bataa nga naay mabal-an bisan gamay, ang bata kung dili gyud siya mo kaon ana imong gi pakaon unsa may problema ana di na mana gyud nato na shoulder kay atoa na mang gibuhad ang tanan.” (IDI-01)

(Do not let yourself be stressed by the child's behavior. Instead of feeling stressed, focus on understanding the child's ways. If the child refuses to eat what you offer, it is not our burden to shoulder because we are doing everything we can.)

In the interview, Violet (pseudonym) openly shared her experience of encountering frustration and stress while dealing with her son's behavior, particularly his stubbornness. However, she adopts a compassionate approach by reminding herself of her son's uniqueness and the need for her to be the one to understand and support him as his mother. She said:

“usahay dili gyud malikayan nga saputon ko sa iyahang kagahi ug ulo pero mahuna-hunaan na lang pud nako nga lahi man siya sa uban datap ako na lang gyud pud ang mo sabot kay ako man iyang mama.” (IDI-02)

(Sometimes, I cannot avoid feeling frustrated by his stubbornness, but then I remind myself that he is different from others, and I should be the one to understand him because I am his mother.)

Encouraging Mastery and Independence in Learning

Fostering autonomy and mastery in learning is vital for the academic success and overall development of students with autism. By promoting independence and proficiency in various tasks through carefully adjusted levels of difficulty, educators can equip these students with essential life skills that extend beyond the classroom. This emphasizes the importance of providing appropriate challenges that enable students to experience success and build confidence in their abilities.

Despite encountering obstacles in writing and learning, Abacus (pseudonym) presents challenges and extends support to the student with autism, with the goal of helping them achieve mastery in writing their own name. This approach reflects a commitment to fostering independence and skill development in the student's educational journey. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“Dili nato hatagan atong lisod didto ta sa sayon kay kung mao to kanunay ang iyahang ginabuhay ma-master to niya at least kabalo na siya bisan sayon ra kaayo to para nimo, lisod na kaayo to para niya kanang mag gunit lang daan ug lapis ana lisod na man gali unsa na lang ang pag purma sa iyahang ngalan.” (IDI-01)

(We should not give them difficult tasks right away; if they always do what they are used to, they will master it even if it seems very simple to you. It becomes very challenging for them if you ask them to do something new, like using a pencil, which can be difficult for them. Imagine how hard it is for them to practice writing their name.)

Curriculum Adaptation

Adapting the curriculum to offer vital support for these students is crucial, aligning with the guidelines set forth in DepEd Order 21 Series of 2023. While the process of removing letters that DepEd deems unnecessary can be challenging. The drawback of this approach lies in the potential negative effects on students' language acquisition and literacy development.

Abacus (pseudonym) underscores the importance of visual aids like flashcards for student retention and learning. Her adaptive teaching approach caters to diverse learning styles, using innovative methods to create engaging learning environments. By emphasizing visual tools, she enhances understanding and retention while promoting inclusive teaching practices for all students. She stated:

“Gipa tanggal biya ni sa deped ang mga gipang pilit no, sa wala pa gipatanggal perteng daghana sa mga gipang pilit ani dako to ug tabang kay maka identify ang mga bata sa mga colors, sa mga shapes kana akong mga letters, dihaa ra na sa ibabaw unya kay ipa tanggal man jud sa supervisor edi pag mag klase ko ipilit nako sa pisara dili nako na kuhaon hangtod dili ko mahuman sa akong mga lesson sa letters kay taga klase nako ana akoa jud na silang reviewhon “any idea unsa ni nga letter? unsay sound ani?” anaon man nako na sila.” (IDI-01)

(The Department of Education's (DepEd) decision to remove visual aids has had a significant impact. These aids were incredibly helpful in engaging children, allowing them to easily identify colors, shapes, and letters. However, we face a challenge when the supervisor insists on removing these aids. So, during my lessons, I simply paste them in front of the class and leave them up until I complete my letter lessons. This is because I always include a review section in my classes, where I ask the students, "Does anyone know what letter this is? What sound does it make?".)

Familial Support and Involvement in Educational Endeavors

The crucial role of family members in supporting the learning and development of students with autism is widely encouraged. During interviews for my study, Abacus (pseudonym), an experienced educator, emphasized the importance of family involvement in the learning process. Family members, by providing understanding, patience, and encouragement, can significantly impact the educational journey and overall well-being of their loved ones with autism.

Abacus (pseudonym), the teacher, demonstrates compassion by encouraging the older sibling to assist the younger one in mastering fundamental skills such as writing their name. Additionally, Abacus emphasizes the crucial role of family support in the educational journey of students with autism, highlighting the collaborative efforts needed to enhance the academic and developmental progress of these students. She stated:

“Manugon na lang pud ko nga “day, tudloi imong manghod didto day ha? pasulata ug pangalan.” tuod nay pangalan ang papel pag skwela pero kabalo ko nga dili man iyang agi kay dili man kabalo mo sulat ang bata.” (IDI-01)

(Day, teach your younger sibling there, okay? Let them write their name." Even if there is a name on the paper, but I know that it is not his writing because the child does not know how to write.)

In certain situations, the older sibling or parent accompanies the younger child to school. This arrangement allows for a supportive environment where the older sibling can aid in teaching the younger one essential skills like reading and writing under parental supervision. By involving family members in the educational journey, such as the older sibling providing mentorship. Violet (pseudonym) stated:

“Usahay ako o iyang ate mo hatod ana sa iyaha sa skwelahan kay grade 6 na man sad iyang ate ba so I hapit ra siya sa room. Gina tudloan sab usahay ug basa ug sulat sa maguwang.” (IDI-02)

(At times, either I or her older sister would accompany her to school since her sister is already in Grade 6 and their classrooms are close by. Additionally, the older sibling occasionally assists her in learning how to read and write under parental guidance.)

Professional Development of Educators

The focus on Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation (MPRE) and seminars for educators, particularly the Special Education (SPED) teacher, reflects a commitment to professional development within the educational context. The SPED teacher's practice of reechoing seminar demonstrates a proactive approach to implementing specialized knowledge and skills acquired through training. The utilization of resources like USBs for presentations indicates a dedication to enhancing teaching practices and fostering a dynamic learning environment.

Abacus (pseudonym) emphasizes ongoing professional development through activities like the Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation (MPRE) and seminars. Sharing insights from seminars, including discussions on Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) and Lower Order Thinking Skills (LOTS), fosters a culture of continuous learning and collaboration among educators. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“Naa man mi mag MPRE (Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation) naa mi seminar, parehas anang kanang SPED teacher dinha kung naa na siyay seminar gina re-echo na niya kay kana iyang bata diha halo2 man gud. Kana pung mga HOTS mga LOTS nga ilang gina seminaran. Tanan gikan sa pag sugod sa klase hantod pagka February na ilang gi seminaran amo nang paminawon ilang mga gipang seminaran parehas atong si SPED teacher naa to siyay gi seminaran sa mga bata nga kanang naay autism. Naa mana silay mga USB ilaha nang ipang show didto.” (IDI-01)

(We have the Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation (MPRE) and seminars, just like that SPED teacher. When there is a seminar, she reechoes it to us. Her students are diverse. They cover topics like HOTS and LOTS in their seminars. From the start of the class until February, they conduct these seminars. We listen to all their seminar discussions, similar to our SPED teacher who had a seminar for children with autism. They also have USBs to use for presentations there.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of the teachers' teaching students with special educational needs when using different strategies to cater the needs of the students?

This question focuses on the understanding teachers gain from the difficulties, hardships, and complexities they encounter while instructing students with special educational needs using various methods to meet the students' requirements. By delving into the insights derived from these hurdles, educators can enhance their teaching techniques continuously and establish an inclusive educational setting that nurtures the achievement and welfare of every student. The key themes included: individualized teaching strategies, building positive teacher-student relationship, special education placement, training for teachers.

Individualized Teaching Strategies

During an interview for my study, Abacus (pseudonym), a seasoned educator, underscored the critical importance of tailoring teaching strategies to meet the unique needs of students with autism. This involves implementing personalized approaches that consider individual strengths, challenges, and learning styles. The use of individualized teaching methods, such as visual supports and structured routines, can significantly enhance engagement and learning outcomes for students with autism.

In the interview, it was revealed that the teacher demonstrates individualized teaching strategies by adapting activities to suit the student's needs, such as using coloring books, crayons, and patterns to engage the student in hands-on learning. Encouraging the student to draw shapes like triangles and circles, the teacher provides personalized guidance and positive reinforcement to enhance the student's understanding and enjoyment. This is proven when Abacus (pseudonym) said that:

“So lahi gyud akong activity jud para sa iyaha, kanang mga coloring book mga ing ana. pwede sab mi mo gamit ug krayola para murag mo tingkad iyang panan aw ba kay color2 na.” (IDI-01)

(So, I have a different activity specifically for him, like coloring books and such. We can also use crayons to make it visually appealing because of the various colors.)

Building Positive Teacher-Student Relationship

Establishing a positive teacher-student relationship is essential for creating a supportive and engaging learning environment for students with autism. During an interview, Abacus (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of building trust, respect, and understanding between the teacher and student. Abacus (pseudonym) shared that when a positive relationship is established, students feel valued, motivated, and more inclined to participate actively in their education.

During the interview, Abacus (pseudonym) stresses the significance of fostering a positive relationship with the autistic child and holding their hand to provide support and comfort. Ensuring the child feels secure and free from fear, Abacus's nurturing and motherly approach from the start aims to establish trust and a sense of safety in their interactions. She stated:

“Mag answer pud siya diha sa among activity ako pud ng gunitan iyang kamot. kinahanglan nga ang ilahang sympathy pag tan aw sa

akoa is dili sila ma hadlok kay mao na nga 1st pa lang daan ipakita na nako sa ilaha nga motherly gyud.” (IDI-01)

(When he answers to the activity, I also hold his hand. It is necessary that their sympathy towards me is that they should not be afraid because as early as the 1st time, I show them that I am really motherly.)

Special Education Placement

In the interview with Abacus (pseudonym), she stressed the importance of advocating for the placement of students with autism in Special Education (SPED) when appropriate, recognizing that these students may require specialized support and a tailored educational environment to thrive. Abacus highlighted the expertise of SPED teachers in understanding and supporting students with autism, suggesting that their specialized knowledge can significantly benefit these learners.

The recommendation for the child's placement in Special Education (SPED) is coupled with a strategic approach outlined by the SPED teacher, proposing a transition to a non-graded system by Grade 3. The plan is for the child to graduate in Grade 6, allowing them to reintegrate into mainstream education after receiving specialized support. Abacus (pseudonym) said:

“Dapat didto na na siya sa SPED, tapos si SPED teacher dili man pud mo dawat ug dili pa daw mo abot sa grade 3 mahulog na na siya nga non-graded, I graduate na lang jud na nila ug grade 6 usa na siya maka balik balik ug skwela.” (IDI-01)

(It is necessary for the child to be placed in SPED (Special Education), and the SPED teacher refused and told me to wait until Grade 3 for the child to be non-graded. They will just graduate the child in Grade 6 so that they can return to regular schooling.)

Training for Teachers

Training mainstream teachers on autism is crucial for creating inclusive classrooms that support the unique needs of students with autism. Abacus, a teacher interviewed, emphasizes the importance of such training, stating that it equips teachers with the knowledge and skills to create inclusive environments, implement effective teaching strategies, and address the individual needs of students with autism.

During the interview, Abacus (pseudonym) highlighted how the SPED teacher imparts knowledge gained from seminars. The SPED teacher utilizes USBs with videos showcasing activities tailored for children with autism, emphasizing practical and visual learning approaches. This collaborative sharing of resources and strategies enhances the educators' ability to support students with autism effectively in the learning environment. Abacus (pseudonym) mentioned:

“Si SPED teacher naa to siyay gi seminaran iya ng I sulti about sa iyang gi seminar sa mga bata nga kanang naay autism. Naa mana silay mga USB ilaha ng ipang show didto ang video kasagaran jud anang mga autism hatagan ra jud na sila ug mga dulaan.” (IDI-01)

(The SPED teacher who attended the seminar shared about what they learned regarding teaching children with autism. They have USBs with videos that they use to share it with us demonstrate different activities specifically designed for children with autism.)

ARTIST

In this distinctive case study, a single female, Teacher III with extensive teaching experience found herself facing a unique challenge in her mainstream classroom. The participant's co-teacher, also female, collaborated closely as they navigated the complexities of educating a student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Unlike typical scenarios, this student presented exceptional difficulties as he frequently exhibited uncooperative behaviors, including consistently sleeping in class and having disruptive tantrums.

The research explored the unique teaching styles, strategies, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of the educator in supporting a student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in an inclusive educational environment. Insights from both the teacher and co-teacher offered valuable perspectives on the specialized techniques necessary to effectively facilitate the learning and development of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

Research Question No. 1: What are the unique teaching styles and strategies of the teachers teaching students with special educational needs?

This question aimed to explore the distinctive teaching styles and strategies utilized by the teacher in addressing the educational needs of a student with special needs, specifically Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). The challenges faced, from managing disruptive behaviors to addressing the unique needs of each student, highlight the dedication and adaptability required in teaching students with special needs. The interviewees' emphasis on understanding, patience, and personalized approaches reflects the essential qualities needed to effectively teach and support students with special needs. In the responses of the two participants, there were five emerging themes that the researcher had found. The following themes are: promoting understanding and acceptance of student with autism, individualized engagement strategies, utilizing basic technology for educational enhancement, adaptation of positive reinforcement strategies, utilizing manipulative objects for engaging learning experiences.

Promoting Understanding and Acceptance of Student with Autism

Educators must prioritize welcoming students with special educational needs and foster an atmosphere of acceptance among all

students. Artist (pseudonym) stated that it is essential to recognize that not all students may fully comprehend the challenges faced by their autistic peers. One of the roles of the teacher is to have an inclusive and positive environment for students with autism. Therefore, teachers play a vital role in educating students about the unique situation of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), emphasizing that their needs and behaviors differ from those of typically developing children.

Through fostering awareness and understanding, educators sow the seeds of empathy, respect, and inclusivity among students, nurturing a culture of compassion and support within the educational community. This approach is pivotal in shaping a harmonious and inclusive learning environment where every individual feels valued, accepted, and empowered to thrive and succeed. As stated by Artist (pseudonym):

“As an educator first is kailangan I welcome siya and aside from that dili man jud siya malikayan nga there are some students nga who really does not understand the situation of the autistic learner so as a teacher there is a need for them to let them understand the situation so ipaunawa sa mga bata nga ang situation nila ay kakaiba kaysa sa situation ng isang bata with autism.” (IDI-03)

(As an educator, it is essential to welcome them, and furthermore, it is crucial to acknowledge that some students may not fully grasp the challenges faced by learners with autism. Therefore, as a teacher, there is a need to help students understand that the situation of individuals with autism is different from that of typically developing children.)

The importance of creating a welcoming environment for students with special educational needs, such as those with Autism, is emphasized in the statement. Making these students feel like they belong and ensuring they are understood, even when they face challenges, is crucial. Sometimes, all they need is someone who can empathize with them and comprehend their difficulties, highlighting the significance of empathy and inclusivity in supporting students with diverse learning needs. This is stated by Bubble (pseudonym) that:

“Oo, I agree with her. It is crucial really for students with special educational needs like with Autism to make them feel welcome. Kumbaga, ipa feel sab nimo sa ilaha nga belong sila. Sometimes man sab gud need lang gyud pud nila ug someone nga maka sabot sa ilaha bisan lisod sila sabton.” (IDI-04)

(Yes, I agree with her. It is crucial for students with special educational needs like Autism to feel welcome. It is like making them feel that they belong. Sometimes, they just really need someone who understands them, even when they are difficult to deal with.)

Individualized Engagement Strategies

To effectively engage students with autism, educators must implement individualized strategies that respect their unique needs and learning styles. Artist (pseudonym) exemplifies this approach by providing tailored activities aligned with the student's capabilities and integrating them into group tasks within their comfort zone. By respecting the student's choices and readiness, educators can create an inclusive learning environment that promotes both academic and social growth.

Artist (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of customizing activities for engagement, ensuring the student's involvement in group tasks within their abilities. She highlighted the significance of honoring the student's choices and readiness, avoiding pressure. This approach prioritizes the student's comfort and autonomy, fostering a supportive learning environment. Her insights underscore the power of personalized strategies in nurturing the student's development. She stated:

“With the simpler activities provided letting him to engage like I apil lang jud siya sa mga group activities yung kaya lang niya pero pag time na dili siya gusto dili nako siya pugson.” (IDI-03)

(By offering simpler activities and encouraging his participation in group activities within his comfort level, I ensure that he engages to the best of his abilities. However, if he shows disinterest at times, I refrain from forcing him to participate.)

Bubble (pseudonym) echoed Artist's (pseudonym) emphasized the challenges faced by students with special needs who struggle to keep pace with their peers. She highlighted the importance of inclusivity and providing tailored activities that cater to their abilities while maintaining their engagement. Bubble stressed the need to ensure these students feel valued and supported within the classroom.

“Lisod man gud ug dili sila lahion kay sagaran jud dili mana sila maka sabay sa other students so, ang strategy jud ana nila kay lahion unya hatagan sila ug ilaha nga ka busyhan na activities na kanang sibo pud sa iyaha.” (IDI-04)

(It is really difficult if they are not being separated because most of the time they cannot keep up with the other students. So, the strategy for them is to include them and give them activities that are suitable for them and at the same time engaging.)

Utilizing Basic Technology for Educational Enhancement

Technology, such as TVs and PowerPoint presentations, can be particularly beneficial for students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) as it enhances visual learning experiences, often preferred by individuals with autism. However, Artist (pseudonym) shared that she uses PowerPoint presentations for basic instructions, the potential for technology to support students with autism extends beyond simple presentations. Exploring a wider range of technology tools, such as interactive software and visual aids, could further enhance learning experiences.

Utilizing basic technology like TVs and PowerPoint slides, the educational approach offers a simplified, non-interactive experience for students with restricted access to laptops reserved for teacher use. The focus is on passive viewing of content through PowerPoint presentations, ensuring structured instruction and enhanced comprehension. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“With the simple technology lang ano lang man ang ginagamit tv lang, powerpoint by simply by viewing lang gyud sila not to the extent na mag manipulate gali sila ug laptop for teacher use lang gyud na so ang technology is kanang powerpoint lang, powerpoint slide. (IDI-03)

(We utilize basic technology such as a TV and PowerPoint presentations for visual learning. The students simply view the content without engaging in hands-on manipulation, and laptops are solely for teacher use. The technology primarily involves PowerPoint slides for instructional purposes.)

Adaptation of Positive Reinforcement Strategies

Artist (pseudonym) recognizes the importance of positive reinforcement strategies in supporting students with autism. She understands that tailoring incentives to their unique needs and challenges is crucial for promoting engagement, motivation, and skill development. As shared by Artist, positive reinforcement can be applied to all students, including those with autism, through simple strategies like praising good behavior.

Positive reinforcement, a potent teaching tool, rewards favorable behaviors to encourage their repetition. In this case, its limited use is attributed to the student's persistent sleeping in class. The classmates' understanding and acceptance of the student's autism, acknowledging differences in engagement, foster an inclusive and supportive classroom environment. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“Specifically positive reinforcement is ano lang jud wala kayo nako nagamit is because iyahang behavior man gud siya sleeping lang gyud siya iyang behavior is always sleep lang gyud during the class so, the positive reinforcement is not only for the special sa iyaha but to those really normal na mga studyante very good syempre by praising him mao na iyang murag basic lang na positive reinforcement na pwede ra gyud sa iyaha.” (IDI-03)

(I did not use positive reinforcement specifically because the student consistently sleeps during class. Positive reinforcement is not only for the student with special needs but also for the typically developing students by praising good behavior. This form of positive reinforcement can be effective for the student.)

Employing positive reinforcement by combining verbal encouragement with tangible rewards, educators aim to reinforce positive behaviors, cultivate a sense of achievement. This strategy is designed to enhance motivation, recognize students' contributions, and encourage active engagement in various learning tasks. Bubble (pseudonym) also implements positive reinforcement with her students by praising them. She stated:

“By telling “wow, good job!” usahay naa sad koy pa candies sa ilaha para lang gyud nga mo participate.” (IDI-04)

(By telling 'wow, good job!' sometimes I also have candies for them to encourage participation.)

Utilizing Manipulative Objects for Engaging Learning Experiences

For students with autism, the use of manipulatives can enhance comprehension, facilitate communication, and support skill development in a structured and engaging manner. Artist (pseudonym) understands that these tangible tools provide hands-on sensory stimulation and visual-tactile feedback, promoting interactive and experiential learning.

Integrating art elements like paintings, colors, and manipulative objects such as popsicle sticks or dice can offer interactive and stimulating educational experiences for students. These creative tools not only enhance numeracy skills but also serve as engaging resources to captivate and entertain the student during learning sessions. By combining art with numeracy activities, educators can create a dynamic and multisensory learning environment that promotes both skill development and enjoyment in the educational journey. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“more on art works like paintings, colors, manipulative objects and if numbers or numeracy man gani kanang mga popsicle sticks na ihapon ba niya or dices para lang mag entertain sa iyaha.” (IDI-03)

(Incorporating art activities like paintings, colors, and manipulative objects such as popsicle sticks or dice can serve as engaging educational tools to enhance numeracy skills and entertain the student.)

Bubble (pseudonym) emphasizes the effectiveness of manipulatives for children with autism stems from their preference for interactive learning experiences over passive instruction. Engaging in activities like games, play, exploring colors, and utilizing real objects captures their interest and promotes active participation. By incorporating hands-on and interactive elements, educators can create a dynamic and engaging learning environment that resonates with the unique learning styles of children with autism. She stated:

“Ang effective jud anang mga bata nga naay autism kay mga manipulatives jud. Dili kaayo na sila kuan anang mga more into interaction bitaw mas ganahan mana sila ug mga games, mag dula2 unya mga colors2 then mga realia.” (IDI-04)

(Children with autism respond well to manipulatives. They are not really keen on just being told; they prefer interactive activities like games, playing, exploring colors, and using real objects.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of teachers when utilizing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs in a classroom?

This question focuses on the teachers' encounters while implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs. Teachers' diverse experiences, challenges, struggles, and difficulties shape their methods and effectiveness. These factors can vary based on students' specific needs, available resources, and the support received from the school and community. The identified themes include: comforting and supporting students with autism during tantrums and discomfort, lack of student engagement, lack of specific training for teachers who are not specialized in special education (SPED), and negative interactions and bullying among peers.

Comforting and Supporting Students with Autism during Tantrums and Discomfort

During the interview, Artist (pseudonym) and Bubble (pseudonym) recognize the importance of providing a safe and understanding environment for students with autism, particularly during moments of tantrums or discomfort. The educators understand that by offering empathy, patience, and understanding, they can build trust and relationships with students, promoting a sense of security and enhancing their ability to regulate emotions and navigate difficult situations.

When a student with autism experiences tantrums or discomfort, providing comfort and support is crucial. Despite personal limitations in assisting during such moments, offering reassurance and comfort, like massaging the student's head to alleviate pain, can be beneficial. Encouraging the student to eat, as it may act as a form of reinforcement and relaxation, can help them feel relieved and calm. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“Kana lang pag ano mag tantrum siya kay even me I cannot help him but kanang to say relax lang, relax I comfort siya like pag mag sakit iyang ulo gina massage nako iyang ulo para ma relieve siya tas sige na kaon lang kay murag iyang reinforcement no kay pag mo kaon siya kay ma relieve, ma relax siya yes mao na akong na notice sa iyaha mao ra gyud akong ma tabang sa iyaha sa iyahang situation.” (IDI-03)

(When he has a tantrum, even I cannot help him, but I try to say 'relax, relax,' and I comfort him. Like when he gets a headache, I massage his head to help him feel better. And then I encourage him to eat because it seems to be a kind of reinforcement for him. When he eats, he feels relieved and relaxed. That is what I have noticed about him, and that is how I can help him in his situation.)

Bubble (pseudonym) expressed the significant difficulty in managing students with autism, particularly during moments of unruliness and disruption in class, can be highly demanding. It requires a careful approach of calming them down effectively, engaging in supportive dialogue, providing reassurance, and encouraging them to remain in place. She stated:

“Lisod jud na sila I handle labi na ug mag wild na bitaw na sila kay grabe jud kalabad sa klase need na sad na nimo sila tarong tarongon ug storya unya pahilomon ingnon na okay ra na, pag puyo ra diha.” (IDI-04)

(It is really challenging to handle them, especially when they become unruly and disruptive in class. You have to calm them down properly, talk to them, reassure them that everything is okay, and ask them to stay put.)

Lack of Student Engagement

Artist (pseudonym) recognizes the challenges faced by students with autism in engaging with traditional teaching methods. She understands that these students may experience difficulties that lead to decreased participation and involvement in educational activities. This is particularly evident in the case of one student who consistently sleeps in class and exhibits behavioral problems.

When the student expresses a desire to sleep, they tend to lie down and remain unresponsive throughout the school day, often spending the entire morning sleeping. In such instances, the student's participation in class activities and discussions is minimal, highlighting the need for tailored support and strategies to enhance their engagement and involvement in the learning process. As stated by Artist (pseudonym):

“si J(student with autism) man gud is not participative, dili jud siya participative for the whole duration sa iyang time ano lang jud siya sleep jud siya ano wala jud siya seldom lang siya mo tingog mo tingog lang siya kung naa siyay needs.” (IDI-03)

(“J, a student with autism, is not participative. Throughout the whole duration of the class, he tends to sleep and remains inactive. He seldom speaks, only when he has specific needs.”)

Bubble (pseudonym) shared that while some students with autism may exhibit noisy behavior, this particular student stands out for being quiet and reserved, lacking significant interaction with others. Observing his reserved nature, it is evident that he may struggle with engaging in social interactions compared to more vocal peers. Understanding these individual differences is crucial in providing tailored support to encourage his participation and foster his social development within the classroom setting. She said:

“Naay uban na mga autism student na sabaan pero kato man gud siya na student kay kanang hilomon then nabantayan sab nako na wala kaayo siyay interaction bitaw. (IDI-04)

(Some students with autism may sometimes appear noisy, but that student is different, he is quiet and reserved. I have observed that he do not engage much in interactions.)

Lack of Specific Training for Teachers Who Are Not Specialized in Special Education (SPED)

The lack of specialized training for teachers not specialized in Special Education (SPED) presents obstacles in adequately meeting the diverse needs of students with special educational requirements. Without targeted training, educators may struggle to implement effective strategies tailored to the unique demands of these students. Addressing this gap is critical through offering professional development opportunities and resources to empower teachers with the essential skills and knowledge needed to establish inclusive and supportive learning environments for all students.

Teachers without specialized training in Special Education (SPED) face challenges in supporting students with special needs, resorting to guesswork and trial-and-error methods. This underscores the importance of targeted professional development to equip educators with effective strategies for inclusive classroom practices. Despite the limitations, teachers strive to provide optimal support for all students. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“Wala sab mi training as teacher nga dili mga sped teacher, wala pud miy training ana amoa lang jud nahulog ra mi nga tagna2 ani nga unsa kaha ni siya of course sa strategy pud kumbaha mag trial and error mi.” (IDI-03)

(We don't have any training as teachers, especially not for special education. We were just thrown into this, figuring it out as we go along, trying different strategies and learning through trial and error.)

Bubble (pseudonym) noted the difficulties of managing students with special needs within mainstream environments, emphasizing the necessity for specialized training in special education to effectively meet the diverse learning needs of these students. She stressed the importance of creating inclusive and supportive learning environments that cater to the unique requirements of students with special educational needs. She expressed:

“Yes, usahay maka ingon sab ko uy na kanang lisod siya labi na kay kanang mas sanay mi nga mainstream biya no wala man sab ta ga kuan ug klase na one-size-fits-all pero man gud mura man ug feel nako dili kaayo mi enough guro para sa mga bata na ing ana kay specialization man gud na sa sped no then kami, we are not trained and skilled to handle students like that.” (IDI-04)

(Yes, sometimes I also think that it is challenging, especially because we are more accustomed to mainstream settings we do not say that there is a one-size-fits-all approach. However, I feel that we may not have enough expertise since handling students with specialized needs requires.”

Negative Interactions and Bullying Among Peers

Artist (pseudonym) and Bubble (pseudonym) recognize the vulnerability of students with autism to bullying and negative interactions, acknowledging the reality that even with their best efforts, instances of hurtful behavior can occur. They understand that while they strive to create a compassionate and inclusive environment that fosters empathy, respect, and awareness, some students may still engage in hurtful behavior.

As Artist (pseudonym) expressed, for students with autism, experiencing hurtful words and bullying from peers can be particularly distressing due to their difficulties in understanding social cues. This underscores the critical need for educators to create a safe and supportive environment that actively addresses instances of mistreatment. As Artist (pseudonym) expressed:

“Ang mga students dili man gud mapigilan na mag bully man gud sila, still naa gyud gihapon like mo ingon sila sa ilang classmate na ka ayahay.” (IDI-03)

(Students cannot be completely prevented from bullying; there are still instances where they may say hurtful things to their classmates.)

Children may notice the varying treatment towards them and students with autism, potentially triggering instances of bullying. This disparity in intervention underscores the importance of creating a unified and supportive approach to combat bullying, ensuring that all students, including those with autism, feel respected and protected within the school environment. As stated by Bubble (pseudonym):

“Makita man gud sa mga bata nga naay different treatment for them and to the student with autism so maybe that is why naa jud mga bullying incidents na mahitabo pero naa man sab si teacher to settle no pero syempre not all the time man gyud na naa perme.” (IDI-04)

(Children can observe the different treatment given to them and to students with autism, which may lead to bullying incidents. However, there are teachers who intervene to address these situations, but of course, it is not always present.)

Research Question No. 3: How did the teachers cope with the challenges faced in implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs?

Participants were questioned about the coping strategies they used to address challenges in implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs. Analysis of their responses identified four primary coping mechanisms: nurturing personal

understanding and managing stress in teaching, simplifies tasks, and collaborative support among educators. These strategies serve as vital tools for educators to navigate the complexities of catering to diverse learning needs, promoting a supportive and effective educational environment for all students.

Nurturing Personal Understanding and Managing Stress in Teaching

Artist (pseudonym) recognizes that effective stress management techniques enable educators to maintain a positive mindset and handle demanding situations with composure, ultimately benefiting both teachers and students. By prioritizing personal understanding and stress management, Artist (pseudonym) can enhance her ability to support students with autism effectively, promoting a positive and inclusive educational experience for all.

Effective stress management helps maintain a positive attitude and handle demanding situations calmly, benefiting both teachers and students. Prioritizing personal understanding and stress management enhances educators' ability to support students with autism effectively, fostering a positive and inclusive educational setting. Artist (pseudonym) said:

Coping mechanism is personal understanding deep understanding that leads to acceptance to the extent na you are willing to cater him regardless sa unsa na situation siya kumbaga ba kanang siguro for me as a teacher, teacher man ko no matter what the situation of the student if may diperensiya man siya or wala.” (IDI-03)

(A coping mechanism is personal understanding, a deep understanding that leads to acceptance to the point where you are willing to cater to him regardless of his situation. It's like, for me as a teacher, I'm a teacher no matter what the situation of the student is, whether they have disabilities or not.)

Breaks Down Tasks Into Manageable Steps

The participant, Artist (pseudonym) understands that breaking down complex activities into smaller, manageable steps is crucial for facilitating understanding and completion, especially for students who may experience cognitive overload. By making tasks more accessible and less overwhelming, Artist empowers students with autism to experience a sense of accomplishment and independence, fostering a positive learning environment where they can thrive.

By providing simplified activities, educators foster an inclusive learning atmosphere that accommodates diverse learning styles. These tasks are tailored to be more manageable, allowing students, including those with autism, to engage effectively with the material. As Artist (pseudonym) expressed, offering simplified tasks promotes active participation and comprehension, ensuring that all students can thrive in the educational setting. She said:

“With the simpler activities provided letting him to engage.” (IDI-03)

(With the simpler activities provided letting him to engage)

According to Bubble (pseudonym), avoiding excessively difficult tasks is crucial to support students in understanding and engaging effectively. Simplifying activities aids in ensuring comprehension and enhancing student participation in the learning process. By offering manageable tasks, educators can promote active involvement and empower students to navigate tasks successfully. She stated:

“Oo, dili na gyud kaayo na sila lisod-lisodon ug mga activities arun masabtan ug ma answeran jud nila ang imong gipabuhat.” (IDI-04)

(Yes, they should no longer be given overly difficult activities so they can better understand and answer what you ask them to do.)

Collaborative Support among Educators

By working together, educators can share expertise, resources, and strategies, ensuring that the student with autism receives the tailored support needed for academic and social growth. Artist (pseudonym) exemplifies this collaborative spirit by actively seeking guidance from previous teachers of students with autism, drawing upon their experience and expertise to enhance her own understanding and approach.

By reaching out to experienced educators who have interacted with the student before, the current teacher can benefit from their insights and strategies in dealing with the student effectively. This collaborative approach fosters a sense of shared knowledge and expertise, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the student's behavior and preferences. Artist (pseudonym) said:

“Asking advice from his previous teachers how did they deal with J (student with autism) so kumbaga nag copy lang ko how to deal with him then siguro since ako not really SPED teacher na knowledgable sa behavior sa bata so kana lang merely asking lang unsa ilang ginabuhat kay J (student with autism) how to comfort him yun lang ana lang Yes, sa principal since aware na sila.” (IDI-03)

(I asked his previous teachers for advice on how they dealt with J (the student with autism). I basically copied their methods for dealing with him. Since I'm not really a special education teacher who is knowledgeable about children's behavior, I just asked them what they did with J, how to comfort him, and things like that. Yes, I also asked the principal since they are aware of his situation.)

Bubble (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of having a support system is valuable in teaching. It is essential not to hesitate to reach out and ask questions, as consulting experts can provide valuable insights and assistance in addressing challenges effectively. By seeking advice from professionals in special education, educators can enhance their teaching practices and better support students with diverse learning needs, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and supportive educational environment. She stated:

“It is good to have someone you can lean on to. In teaching, importante jud na dili ta magpa hawd2 unya mangutana jud ta daan sa mga experts like the sped teachers.” (IDI-04)

(It is good to have someone you can lean on. In teaching, it is crucial not to be hesitant and to ask questions to experts like special education teachers.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of the teachers’ teaching students with special educational needs when using different strategies to cater the needs of the students?

This question delves into the insights of teachers regarding the difficulties and complexities they encounter while employing various strategies to support students with special educational needs. By delving into these challenges, educators can refine their teaching techniques, cultivate an inclusive classroom atmosphere, challenge biases, foster acceptance, engage school psychologists, and offer training for mainstream teachers. This process enables continuous improvement in teaching practices and the creation of a supportive learning environment that nurtures the success and well-being of all students.

Life Skills Development and Individualized Support

Educators like Artist (pseudonym) prioritizes life skills development and personalized support for students with autism. She understands that focusing on these areas equips students with the confidence to tackle daily challenges independently. By fostering self-sufficiency and resilience, Artist (pseudonym) empowers students to navigate life's complexities with autonomy.

Artist (pseudonym) emphasized the significance of nurturing life skills and providing personalized support for students with special educational needs like Autism to foster their independence and autonomy as they progress through life. Transitioning towards independence involves providing the knowledge to handle tasks autonomously, with occasional guidance as needed. She stated:

“Magiging independent jud siya kay autistic biya siya how to keep your things, how to turn on lights, how to turn on and off televisions, how to arrange your things, for long life learning gyud niya kay dili biya siya habang buhay naay mag guide sa iya at least one strategy is letting him do things daily na ginagawa, kabalo siya kailangan lang siya I guide.” (IDI-03)

(He will truly become independent because he is autistic. Teaching him how to organize his belongings, operate lights, TVs, and arrange items fosters lifelong learning. He would not have constant guidance as time goes by at least one strategy is that he learns to do daily tasks independently; he knows what to do, just needing occasional guidance.)

Acceptance and Inclusion

In her educational approach, Artist (pseudonym) embodies the values of acceptance and inclusion. By embracing diversity and recognizing individual differences, she fosters respect and empathy among peers. Celebrating unique strengths and offering essential support, Artist (pseudonym) actively promotes a sense of belonging and positive social interactions for all students.

The initial step involves accepting learners unconditionally, irrespective of their behavioral status or special needs, to foster a culture of respect and understanding. Understanding the individual needs of learners allows for the creation of tailored strategies that provide meaningful experiences, ultimately shaping their perception of the essence of schooling and learning. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“First thing is to accept the learner regardless of his/her behavioral status or learners with special needs then second one is kapaag naintindihan mo na, make some plans na at least maka tulong sa iyaha para maging magkaroon siya ng experiences ba what is really school and what is really learning.” (IDI-03)

(The first step is to accept the learner unconditionally, regardless of their behavioral status or if they have special needs. Once you understand this, create plans to help them gain experiences that define the true essence of schooling and learning.)

Acceptance and inclusion in teaching, especially with diverse learners like students with autism, is crucial for their growth. Making them feel like they belong in the learning environment is essential.

Bubble (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of embracing and integrating these students for a supportive atmosphere. Prioritizing acceptance and inclusion benefits students with autism. She stated:

“In teaching, we have diverse learners man so if naay situation like ing ani na naa tay student na naay autism, it is crucial to accept and welcome them ipa feel sa ilaha nga belong sila.” (IDI-04)

(In teaching, we encounter diverse learners, so if there is a situation where we have a student with autism, it is crucial to accept and welcome them, making them feel that they belong.)

Assessment for Improvement

Artist (pseudonym), a dedicated educator, recognizes the vital role of assessments in supporting the unique needs of students with autism. She understands that while teachers may observe behaviors, formal assessments provide a comprehensive understanding of their strengths and challenges, guiding educators in tailoring their approach to meet each student's individual needs. Artist (pseudonym) is also deeply aware of the obstacles parents often face in accessing these assessments due to financial constraints, which can significantly hinder early identification and intervention.

Teachers recognize potential special needs in students but lack formal assessments due to financial constraints for parents. Doctors' expensive assessments hinder access to necessary evaluations for children with special needs. The plea is for the Department of Education (DepEd) to provide free assessments for all students noted by teachers as requiring special support. This initiative would ensure early interventions and equitable access to support services, fostering inclusive education for all learners. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“Mag hatag sila ug assessment sa mga students kay actually kami no nga mga teachers amoa na lang siyang hunahuna nga siguro naa ni siyay kuan kay lahi iyang behavior pero wala miy legal assessment kay wala may gi hatag na doctor na free unta na mo assess unta sa ilaha sa akong nahibal an kay ginabayran siya ang doctor na mo assess ug expensive daw siya so ang parent dili ka afford so I hope si DepEd mag hatag siya ug assessment na free na I assess tanang bata sa school na nakitaan lang ni teacher na there is something special needs sa bata.” (IDI-03)

(They should provide assessments for the students because actually we teachers just think that maybe the student has something, because their behavior is different. But we do not have any legal assessments because there are not any free doctors who can assess them. As far as I know, you have to pay the doctor to assess them, and it is expensive, so parents cannot afford it. I hope that DepEd will provide free assessments so that all children in school who teachers have identified as having special needs can be assessed.)

Gap In Training For Mainstream Teachers

The absence of specialized development programs for mainstream teachers like Artist (pseudonym) has left dealing with the challenges of supporting students with special needs. The reality of not receiving training as teachers, especially not as Special Education (SPED) teachers, has led to rely solely on guesswork. This underscores the pressing need for targeted professional development opportunities to navigate these challenges and create a more inclusive educational environment for all students, including those with autism.

As untrained teachers, there is a lack of preparation to support diverse learning needs. Without proper training, educators are left to rely on guesswork. This underscores the importance of professional development to enhance skills in catering to diverse educational requirements. Bridging this training gap is crucial for ensuring inclusive and effective education for all students. This is proven by Artist (pseudonym) stating:

“Teacher man ta so tapos wala sab mi training as teacher nga dili mga sped teacher, wala pud miy training ana amoa lang jud nahulog ra mi nga tagna2.” (IDI-03)

(We are teachers but we have not received training as teachers, especially not as Special Education (SPED) teachers. We also did not receive training for that. We are just left on our own with guesswork.)

The absence of prior experience in supporting children with autism, coupled with inadequate training and seminars, poses significant challenges for educators. Without previous encounters with students on the autism spectrum, teachers feel ill-prepared and compare the situation to being thrust into a battle unprepared. The critical necessity for specialized training and professional development to equip educators with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively support students with autism. As stated by Bubble (pseudonym):

“Dili man sab gud kaayo mi hawd mo handle ug ing ana na mga bata kay wa miy ka agi pa sukad nga naay studyante nga naay Autism tapos wala sad biya jud enough no nga mga seminars, training para ana kumbaga diretso na mi naa sa gyera nga walay preparation.” (IDI-04)

(We are not really equipped to handle these kinds of children. We have never had a student with autism before, and there have not been enough seminars or training for this. It is like we are thrown into a war without any preparation.)

EXTRAORDINARY

In this case, there was a single female participant, a Teacher II with over a decade of teaching background, who had a student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in her regular classroom. The informant, also a female, served as the participant's co-teacher. Together with a female co-teacher, they navigated a series of obstacles and adaptations in their roles, with a particular focus on addressing the needs of the student with ASD. Despite the student's tendency to roam around the room during discussions, the teacher observed that he attentively listened, actively participated in gamification activities, and surprised them by answering questions thoughtfully. The teacher's innovative strategies, including tailored approaches and engaging teaching styles, effectively captured the attention of all students, showcasing her creativity and adaptability in supporting diverse learners, especially those with ASD.

This study explored the unique teaching methods, coping strategies, and valuable insights of an educator guiding a student with Autism

Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in an inclusive academic setting. The collaborative insights from both the teacher and the co-teacher provided essential perspectives on specialized techniques crucial for effectively nurturing the learning and development of students with ASD. By prioritizing inclusivity, adapting activities to student preferences, utilizing interactive technology, incorporating manipulative objects and gamification, and fostering positive behavior, the research underscored the profound impact of tailored approaches in fostering a supportive and enriching educational environment for all students, particularly those with special needs.

Research Question No. 1: What are the unique teaching styles and strategies of the teachers teaching students with special educational needs?

This question study sought to discover the unique teaching styles and strategies employed by the teacher when working with a student with special educational needs, particularly Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). This involved tailoring methods to the student's distinct behaviors and needs, such as adjusting seating arrangements and providing personalized activities. The teacher also focused on fostering a supportive and accepting classroom atmosphere, demonstrating patience and persistence to guide the student through tasks. In the responses of the two participants, there were four emerging themes that the researcher had found. The following themes are: fostering an inclusive learning environment, supporting student preferences in differentiated activities, enhancing learning with interactive technology and engaging activities, use of manipulative objects and gamification, and positive reinforcement.

Fostering an Inclusive Learning Environment

In her endeavor to create an inclusive learning environment, Extraordinary (pseudonym) implements vital strategies such as organizing the classroom, promoting calmness, showing love, and managing stress. By prioritizing structure and security, cultivating a serene atmosphere, expressing care, and addressing stress factors, she actively contributes to fostering a supportive learning environment.

Extraordinary, under the pseudonym, emphasized the inherent responsibility to cultivate an inclusive environment, particularly catering to learners with special educational needs, notably those with autism. By acknowledging this duty, she demonstrates a profound commitment to ensuring that all individuals, regardless of their unique requirements, feel welcomed, supported, and included in the learning process. She stated:

“As a teacher, it is my duty to keep my classroom organize then promote a calm and positive environment so that the learner with special educational needs can feel he/she belongs to the class then they should need to feel our love ang bata man gud nga nay autism no kay kanang kinahanglan ma feel nila na naa jud silay love mao na nga imoha sila nga I hug ing ana na sila.” (IDI-05)

(As a teacher, it is my responsibility to keep my classroom organized and promote a calm and positive learning environment. This helps students with special educational needs feel like they belong in the class. They need to feel our love. Children with autism need to feel loved, so I make sure to hug them and show them that they are cared for.)

Additionally, Star (pseudonym) affirms Artist's (pseudonym) viewpoint by articulating their mutual dedication to creating a supportive, nurturing, and inclusive environment for students with special needs, particularly those with autism. She emphasizes the importance of fostering an atmosphere where every student feels valued, respected, and included in the learning process, stating:

“As a co-teacher and friend of Ma’am Artist (pseudonym) nakita jud nako no nga gahimo gyud siya ug positive atmosphere for students with special needs, including those with autism, to feel welcomed and supported.” (IDI-06)

(As a co-teacher and friend of Ma’am Artist (pseudonym) I’ve seen her create a positive atmosphere for students with special needs, including those with autism, to feel welcomed and supported.)

Supporting Student Preferences in Differentiated Activities

Extraordinary (pseudonym) understands the importance of recognizing individual differences in how students process information and engage in learning. She believes that adapting teaching methods to accommodate these variations is crucial for creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment. This ensures that each student's unique needs are met, promoting engagement and comprehension.

The teacher's observance of students preferring video lessons and interactive activities highlights the importance of incorporating engaging and multimedia-rich content to enhance student participation and comprehension. Additionally, honoring students' requests, such as allowing a student with autism to draw instead of write, demonstrates a personalized approach that respects their preferences and abilities, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. Extraordinary (pseudonym) revealed it by stating:

“Every learner has a different learning style man jud, they need differentiated activities. for them as I observe they prefer video lessons, mga interactive video lessons ang ilahang ganahan sa klase. Gina lahi ang iyahang activity kato siya, actually isa lang jud akong bata nga naay autism then usahay mo ingon siya nga “teacher, can I draw?” instead of writing yung activity “Ok, you can draw” we need to give them sa ilahang gusto kay kuan dili man sila pwede, dili sila ka kaya sa mga sulaton like sentence kay kapoyan sila.” (IDI-05)

(Each learner has a unique learning style, and it is crucial to provide differentiated activities to cater to their individual needs. From my observations, students, especially those with autism, often prefer interactive video lessons. I recall one particular student with autism who would sometimes ask, "Teacher, can I draw?" Instead of sticking to the original writing activity, I allowed them to draw as it suited

their preferences better. It is important to accommodate their preferences and capabilities, as they may find certain tasks like writing sentences challenging.)

Enhancing Learning with Interactive Technology and Engaging Activities

Extraordinary (pseudonym) is dedicated to utilizing interactive technology and engaging activities to enhance the learning experience for students with special educational needs. By incorporating elements like singing alphabet songs and interactive presentations, she creates a dynamic and inclusive classroom environment. Her focus on making learning visually appealing and interactive demonstrates her commitment to fostering active participation and ensuring that all students, especially those with special needs, are fully engaged in the learning process.

By incorporating tools like television and PowerPoint presentations, educators can create visually appealing and interactive content that captures the students' interest. Activities such as singing alphabet songs and dancing letters not only cater to different learning styles but also make the learning process enjoyable and dynamic. It is crucial for teachers to ensure that their presentations are not only attractive but also interactive to encourage active participation from all students. Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“Yes, number one ang t.v. jud no to enhance the learning experience of the student with special educational needs so powerpoint presentation pero dapat imong powerpoint presentation kay kanang naa puy mga attractive kay diha mana sila malingaw kanang mga for example singing of alphabet songs ganahan siya atong nay mga kanang mag sayaw2 na mga letters, mao na ilahang ganahan so as a teacher para maka participate siya kauban sa mga bata nga uban so kinahanglan nimo siya nga himoon nga interactive ang imohang activity unya ang imohang presentation kinahanglan dapat pina gwapa gyud siya.” (IDI-05)

(Yes, television is indeed a great tool to enhance the learning experience for students with special educational needs, along with PowerPoint presentations. However, your PowerPoint presentation should be visually appealing to captivate their interest. For example, incorporating activities like singing alphabet songs and dancing letters can be engaging for them. As a teacher, it is essential to ensure that the activities are interactive to encourage participation from all students. Your presentation must be attractive to maintain their engagement effectively.)

Use of Manipulative Objects and Gamification

The integration of interactive technology and hands-on learning strategies, as employed by Extraordinary (pseudonym). This approach recognizes the diverse learning styles and needs of students, particularly those with special educational needs. By incorporating elements like interactive presentations and manipulative objects, Extraordinary creates a multi-sensory learning environment that promotes engagement, comprehension, and retention.

The incorporation of gamification and manipulative objects not only enhances the enjoyment of learning for a student with autism but also encourages active participation and a deep understanding of the lesson material. This approach is tailored to accommodate the unique learning style and individual needs of students with autism, fostering engagement and facilitating a comprehensive grasp of the content within the classroom setting. It is proven and stated by Extraordinary (pseudonym):

“I sometimes introduce my lessons through games, human mo participate na na sila tanan wala pa sila kabalo unsa imong lesson human kay paghuman na mag game, na diha pa nimo I introduce ang lesson sa game, so sa game everyone loves game man jud no so especially sa student with special educational needs ganahan kaayo siya ug dula mas ganahan man sila ug play kaysa sa writing. Kanang using mga manipulative objects jud siya, kana jud ang I apply. Kinahanglan gyud niya kay kanang ma attract jud para mo participate jud siya, once na attracted siya sa imong lesson mo participate siya.” (IDI-05)

(I sometimes introduce my lessons through games, where everyone participates first without knowing the lesson yet. After the game, that is when I introduce the lesson through the game. Everyone loves games, especially students with special educational needs; they enjoy playing more than writing. Using manipulative objects is crucial because that is what I apply. It is essential to attract their attention to ensure active participation. Once they are engaged in the lesson, they become more involved.)

As mentioned by Star (pseudonym), engaging children with autism in activities involving manipulative objects provides them with a tactile and interactive learning experience. These objects not only entertain them but also serve as valuable tools for enhancing their cognitive and sensory development. The hands-on interaction with manipulative objects not only sparks joy in the children but also contributes significantly to their learning process. She stated:

“Ang bagay jud ana sa mga bata nga naay mga autism bitaw kay kana jung mga manipulative objects na ilahang ma gunitan, ma dula-dulaan. Kay malingaw mana sila pero at the same time kay maka learn sad sila.” (IDI-06)

(It is really beneficial for children with autism to engage with manipulative objects that they can hold and play with. It brings them joy and, at the same time, helps them learn.)

Positive Reinforcement

Extraordinary (pseudonym) effectively employs positive reinforcement strategies, recognizing their crucial role in supporting students with autism. By utilizing a combination of verbal praise, non-verbal cues, and tangible rewards, she creates a positive and encouraging

learning environment. This approach not only acknowledges student efforts but also reinforces desired behaviors, ultimately fostering self-esteem and motivation.

Using verbal praise, non-verbal cues like high-fives, thumbs up, and tangible rewards such as candy and star stickers fosters a positive learning environment. These methods acknowledge students' efforts and reinforce desired behaviors, enhancing their confidence and participation. The mix of verbal and non-verbal positive reinforcement nurtures a sense of accomplishment and appreciation among students, fostering a positive classroom atmosphere where they feel valued and motivated to succeed. This is proven by Extraordinary (pseudonym) by stating:

“So I use sometimes verbal praise like “Good job!”, “well done” “very good” then there are times pud na non-verbal ques siya kanang mag high-five mo ganahan kaayo na silag high-five pasabot na appreciate nimo ilahang kuan gud nakatama ba sila I high-five nimo sila, I thumbs up or sometimes kanang mag prepare ko ug candy “who wants candy/chocolates?” kanang star nga I tatak, mga smiley face mao na sila ilahang ganahan.” (IDI-05)

(Sometimes, I provide verbal praise like "Good job!", "Well done," or "Very good." Additionally, I use non-verbal cues such as giving high-fives, thumbs up, or preparing candy or chocolates with star stickers or smiley faces as rewards. Students respond positively to these gestures, showing that they appreciate the recognition when they receive a high-five or a token of appreciation like candy or a star sticker. These methods of positive reinforcement help create a supportive and motivating classroom environment where students feel valued and encouraged to succeed.)

Star (pseudonym) highlights the joy children experience when praised with phrases like "wow, good job," emphasizing that acknowledging their responses boosts their motivation and engagement. This positive reinforcement not only values their efforts but also encourages active participation and a sense of accomplishment, creating a supportive learning environment. She stated:

“Oo uy, malipay na man gyud ang mga bata anang mo ingon ka ug “wow, good job” or unsa pa na diha tapos ug mo tubag sila imoha pa jud na hatagan ug emphasis ug kabug-aton ganahan na mana sila ana.” (IDI-06)

(Yes, children really feel happy when you say 'wow, good job' or something similar, and when they respond, if you emphasize and give weight to their answer, they will like that.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of teachers when utilizing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs in a classroom?

The questions focused on teachers' experiences when implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs, particularly those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), highlighting the challenges and difficulties they encounter. In the participants' responses, four key themes emerged, as identified by the researcher. Challenges in behavior management, importance of collaboration and communication among educators, lack of student participation and engagement in the classroom, and need for continuous learning and professional development.

Challenges in Behavior Management

Extraordinary (pseudonym) demonstrates a deep understanding of the challenges associated with managing challenging behaviors in students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Her approach, characterized by patience, empathy, and the implementation of specialized strategies, aligns with current best practices in supporting students with special educational needs.

The student with autism exhibits challenging behaviors, engaging in severe tantrums like hitting their head against hard surfaces when their desires are not met, causing distress due to the intensity of their actions. Handling these challenging behaviors poses a significant obstacle, complicating efforts to address their emotional reactions and needs effectively within the classroom setting. As stated by Extraordinary (pseudonym):

“mag tantrums jud siya kay I pakog-pakog niya iyang ulo sa semento unya ikaw na ang mahadlok kay ikusog gyud niya pag dili ma kuha iyang gusto. One time akong I.D. kay iyang ingkiton kay nag bitay2 akong I.D. so pag deal jud sa ilahang tantrums, ilahang behavior lisod siya.” (IDI-05)

(He really throws tantrums by banging his head against the concrete, and you get scared because he really hits hard when he does not get what he wants. One time, he even bite my ID card. Dealing with his tantrums is really challenging due to his behavior.)

As highlighted by Star (pseudonym),. The consistent effort required to manage these challenges in a school setting reflects the enduring commitment of parents and caregivers who navigate these issues every day. The ongoing effort required to address these issues reflects the resilience and perseverance of families who confront these obstacles each day. She said:

“Mag lisod na man gali ta no ug deal sa ilahang behavior in school, unsa na lang ang ginikanan ug pamilya ana nga bata nga everyday jud nila gina deal ang mga tantrums ug behavior sa bata.” (IDI-06)

(We might find it challenging to, but imagine the parents and family members who deal with the child's tantrums and behavior every day.)

Importance of Collaboration and Communication Among Educators

During the interview, Extraordinary (pseudonym) recognizes the importance of collaborative learning and professional development in supporting students with special needs. She actively engages in sharing sessions, relaxed discussions, and small group interactions with co-teachers to explore and develop effective strategies tailored to meet the diverse needs of learners. Extraordinary values the expertise of Special Education (SPED) teachers and actively seeks opportunities to collaborate with them, exchanging valuable insights and best practices. This collaborative approach reflects her commitment to continuous learning and the pursuit of best practices in supporting all students.

By engaging in sharing sessions, relaxed discussions, and small group interactions, the teacher collaborates with colleagues to explore effective strategies for teaching students with special educational needs. Through conversations with Special Education (SPED) teachers, they seek expert advice and guidance on implementing appropriate approaches. As Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“Through sharing, relax session or small group discussion I can collaborate with my co-teachers so that we can discuss mga possible nga mga strategies na pwede nako magamit in teaching learners with special educational needs.” (IDI-05)

(Through sharing, relaxed sessions, or small group discussions, I collaborate with my co-teachers to explore possible strategies that I can use in teaching learners with special educational needs.)

Moreover, According to Star (pseudonym), engaging conversations occur. These discussions revolve around identifying effective practices and strategies, recognizing the individualized nature of each child's needs. Acknowledging that what may be successful for one student may not be as effective for another. These brainstorming sessions provide a valuable opportunity to exchange ideas and explore diverse approaches to cater to the unique requirements of each student. She stated:

“Usahay mag chika-chika man jud mi ana nila ma’am labi na ug lunch time kay mag sabay man mi ug kaon, mag hisgot2 mi unsay mga maayo na mga pang buhaton, mga strategies na ilahang gina employ, kay it does not mean biya nga effective ani nga bata tapos sa kini kay dili pud so, akong maingon na naga brain storming sab jud mi.” (IDI-06)

(Sometimes we really have conversations, especially with Ma'am, especially during lunchtime when we eat together. We discuss what good practices to do, what strategies to employ because just because something works for one child does not mean it will work for another. So, I can say we also brainstorm a lot.)

Challenge of Lack of Student Participation and Engagement in The Classroom

Both Extraordinary (pseudonym) and Star (pseudonym) recognize the unique challenges faced by students with Autism, particularly their potential struggles with participation in the classroom. They understand that factors like fatigue, difficulty focusing, and feeling overwhelmed can significantly impact their engagement. Both educators emphasize the importance

Students are given a time limit to work on tasks. When they begin writing, it is beneficial to support their efforts, but if they struggle to write, it is advisable to let them take a break. It is crucial not to pressure them if they are unable to write, as forcing them can be counterproductive and may hinder their progress. Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“Naa ra man gud na silay time limit kung kinus a sila mo lingkod mo buhat, pag mo ingon nga “teacher I am tired, sorry” ok, relax. Kanang if mag sulat, pasagdan lang nimo siya, kung mo sulat siya mas maayo. Pero ug dili siya mag sulat, sige unya na lang. Dili lang nimo pugson. (IDI-05)

(They have a time limit when they sit down to work, and if they say, 'Teacher, I am tired, sorry,' it is okay, just relax. If they start writing, let them be, it is better if they write. But if they cannot write, just let it go. Do not force them.)

In addition, Star (pseudonym) shared that individuals with autism may encounter challenges in verbal communication, impacting their ability to express themselves effectively. This difficulty could lead to reduced participation in class discussions or activities. Understanding and accommodating these communication barriers are essential to support their engagement and learning experience. She stated:

“Dili man gud kaayo na siya mo tingog kay ana pa sila kana dawng mga bata nga naay autism kay naa na sab silay difficulties sa ilang pag storya bitaw na kanang dili sila maka express sa ilang gina bati so maybe that is why dili kaayo siya mo tubag sa klase.” (IDI-06)

(Sometimes he does not speak much because they say children with autism also have difficulties in their communication. They may struggle to express their thoughts, so maybe that is why he does not participate much in class.)

Need for Continuous Learning and Professional Development

Extraordinary (pseudonym) acknowledges the importance of continuous learning and study to better cater to the needs of students with diverse learning profiles. Extraordinary (pseudonym) actively seeks opportunities to enhance her knowledge and skills, recognizing that understanding and supporting these students is an ongoing process. Her commitment to professional growth reflects her dedication to providing the best possible educational experience for all students, including those with Autism.

Extraordinary (pseudonym) expressed challenges in working with students with special educational needs, specifically a student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). She found it difficult to comprehend the student's behavior due to its unfamiliarity, prompting her to dedicate time to study and understand how to effectively interact with the student. Extraordinary (pseudonym) said:

“Lisod siya sa akong part kay usahay kay dili ka maka sabot pag pirmero so kailangan jud ka mag study para sa ilaha.” (IDI-05)

(It is difficult for me in my role because sometimes I struggle to understand them at first, so it is necessary for me to study for them.)

Research Question No. 3: How did the teachers cope with the challenges faced in implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs?

In the third question, participants were questioned about their coping strategies for challenges encountered while implementing teaching techniques for students with special educational needs. Analysis of their responses identified four primary coping mechanisms: clear and simple instructions, seeking advice and guidance from experienced educators, the value of patience and empathy in handling challenging situations, and parental involvement in creating a supportive and understanding environment for the child's development.

Clear and Simple Instructions

Extraordinary (pseudonym) prioritizes the use of clear and straightforward instructions to support students with Autism. By incorporating visual aids and structured routines, she enhances comprehension and engagement while promoting independence and autonomy in their academic pursuits. Extraordinary's emphasis on clarity and simplicity aligns with best practice, ensuring that students with Autism can effectively grasp information and navigate tasks with confidence.

Through simplifying and clarifying instructions, educators can ensure that students understand the tasks more easily and quickly. Complex or lengthy instructions may pose challenges for students with diverse learning needs, emphasizing the effectiveness of using straightforward and clear language to enhance comprehension and engagement in the learning process. Extraordinary (pseudonym) said:

“So, I think is to modify the instructions, make the instruction clear and simple para maka kuan sila maka gets dayun kay ug imoha siyang I taas ra kaayo ug instructions sa ilaha dili mana nila ma kuan so mas mayo gyud tong simple unya clear.” (IDI-05)

(So, I believe that modifying instructions by making them clear and simple is essential. When instructions are too long or complex, students may struggle to understand them immediately. It is more effective to use simple and clear instructions to ensure that students grasp the information quickly and easily.)

In discussing this, Star (pseudonym) underscores the significance of customizing teaching methods to align with students' unique learning capacities. By acknowledging and adjusting to their individual comprehension levels, educators can guarantee that the content is not only suitable but also captivating for maximal learning effectiveness. She emphasized:

“You do not have to make things complicated for them. Kailangan kabalo sab ka sa ilahang level of learning so that ikaw as a teacher maka bana-bana ka nga ay kini dili pa kaayo siya pwede ani kay complex ra kaayo so akong strategy is to adjust it according to their level.” (IDI-06)

(You do not have to make things complicated for them. You need to understand their level of learning so that as a teacher, you can assess that this might be too advanced for them because it is too complex. My strategy is to adjust it according to their level.)

Seeking Advice and Guidance from Experienced Educators

In the realm of education, it is essential to seek guidance from seasoned professionals rather than making impulsive decisions. According to Extraordinary (pseudonym), these professionals possess a deep understanding of the unique needs of students with diverse learning styles and can provide invaluable insights and strategies. Their years of experience offer valuable perspectives and practical solutions to challenges faced in the classroom. By collaborating with these experts, teachers can ensure that students receive the appropriate support they need to thrive.

The strategy of seeking advice and guidance from experienced educators, particularly master teachers and Special Education (SPED) teachers, plays a vital role in professional growth and effective teaching practices. By consulting with educators who have specialized training and practical experience in supporting students with diverse learning needs, teachers can benefit from valuable insights and strategies that have been proven effective in the field. Extraordinary (pseudonym) said:

“I usually seek advice from our master teachers so naa man miy mga master teacher diri daghan then most specially sa SPED teachers jud kay sila man ang naka skwela ana no ug unsaon so mas maayo mana nga dili ta mag buot2 ba pwede gud ta maka search pero mas maayo gyud nang nay maka advise sa imoha kay sila may nay experience. Yes, sa principal kanang mga ing-ana sa mga meetings pwede nimo ma raise ang imohang problema ana lang siya.” (IDI-05)

(I usually seek advice from our master teachers because we have many master teachers here, especially the Special Education (SPED) teachers because they are the ones trained in that field and know how to handle it. It is better not to act impulsively, right? We can search, but it is really better if someone can advise you because they have the experience. Yes, with the principal, in those meetings,

you can raise your issues, that is the only way.)

The Value of Patience and Empathy in Handling Challenging Situations

When working with students with autism, understanding their behavior is essential. As Extraordinary (pseudonym) emphasizes, patience and empathy are key to creating a supportive learning environment. Teachers must strive to understand the unique needs of these students and respond with patience and compassion, rather than frustration. By providing necessary support and understanding, teachers can help students navigate challenges and feel secure in their learning environment. Empathy allows teachers to connect with students on a deeper level.

Showing love and giving extra attention to the student with autism, can make them feel valued and understood. Extraordinary (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of understanding and showing love to students, particularly those with unique needs. This approach creates a sense of belonging and encourages individuals to thrive. Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“First is understand their behavior sabton nato sila kay ug dili ta makasabot sa ilaha, masuko man ta sa ilaha, masuko jud ta kay wala nila gi tuman ang imong gi sulti wala sila ni sunod sa imong task na gi hatag so we need to understand them and their behavior unya you need to give them kung gi love nato atong mga studyante, more love pa gyud sa ilaha kay mas kinahanglan na ma feel gyud niya nga mo hatag ka sa iyaha ug more attention kay lahi ra jud biya siya no.” (IDI-05)

(First is to understand their behavior. We need to respond to them because if we do not understand them, we might get upset with them. We might feel frustrated because they did not follow what we said or the task given. So, we need to comprehend them and their behavior. Moreover, we need to show them love. If we love our students, we need to give them even more love because they really need to feel that you are giving them more attention, as they are different.)

Parental Involvement in Creating a Supportive and Understanding Environment for The Child's Development

Active engagement and open communication from parents help student with autism feel heard and supported in their growth journey. This approach encourages children to express themselves freely and explore their individuality, contributing to their emotional well-being and overall development. As Extraordinary (pseudonym) emphasizes, understanding and supporting children's unique needs is vital in fostering a positive and nurturing environment where they can flourish.

Additionally, Extraordinary (pseudonym) emphasized the significance of parental involvement in the advancement of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). She highlighted the importance of parents not denying their child's condition, noting that some mothers may struggle with being open-minded.

However, she praised the child's mother displayed exceptional open-mindedness, allowing for a deeper level of understanding and support for the child. She stated that:

“Oo, parent’s involvement. Dapat gyud sa parent dili siya in denial na ing ana kay naa gyud pud biyay mga mama nga dili ing ana, dili open-minded pero katong bata na kato siya gwapo lang gyud ato iyang nanay mismo open kaayo nga mao nga masabtan jud siya.” (IDI-05)

(Yes, parental involvement. Parents should not be in denial about their child's case because there are mothers who are also not open-minded, but in the case of that child, it is nice because his mother herself is very open-minded, so he is truly understood.)

In agreement with Star (pseudonym) the family, particularly parents or guardians, serves as the primary source of support for teachers. Being there for the child from day one, they possess the deepest understanding of the child. The responsibility of the teacher is to aid, mentor, and educate them on fostering their growth as individuals. She said:

“Ang primary jud na maka tabang sa mga teachers no is the family jud, especially the parents or guardians. Sila biya jud ang kauban sa bata day 1 pa lang so sila ang mas nakaila ug nakasabot sa ilaha. So amoa lang pud is to help them, guide and teach them how to become better individuals.” (IDI-06)

(The primary support for teachers is really the family, especially the parents or guardians. They are the ones who are with the child from day one, so they know and understand them the most. Our role is to assist, guide, and educate them on how to become better individual.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of the teachers’ teaching students with special educational needs when using different strategies to cater the needs of the students?

This question pertains to the understanding teachers gain from the obstacles they face while employing various strategies to meet the needs of students with special educational requirements. It suggests that by reflecting on these challenges, educators can enhance their teaching methods, establish an inclusive classroom setting, and enhance the success and welfare of all students.

The following themes that emerged were: tailoring activities to individual learning needs, overcoming challenges in special education placement and resource provision, bridging the role of school psychologists and medical professionals, enhancing inclusive education through teacher training and support programs, academic and behavioral progress through a supportive learning environment

Tailoring Activities to Individual Learning Needs

As Extraordinary (pseudonym) suggests, using video lessons, differentiated activities, and concrete examples like manipulative materials and toys that mirror their experiences can enhance student engagement and comprehension. By adapting activities to accommodate their sensory sensitivities, communication challenges, and preferred learning styles, educators can create a more accessible and engaging learning experience for students with autism.

By customizing lesson plans to correspond with the unique experiences and strengths of each student, educators have the opportunity to nurture independence, advocate for inclusivity, and facilitate holistic growth in academic and personal domains for students with autism. Extraordinary (pseudonym) emphasized the profound impact it can have on the educational journey of students with autism. As Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“Using video lessons, differentiated activities, so mga concrete examples mga similar sa ilang experiences kung pwede kanang mga manipulative materials, mga toys mga ing-ana mao nay maka kuan sa ilaha.” (IDI-05)

(By using video lessons, differentiated activities, and concrete examples like manipulative materials and toys that mirror their experiences, students can better understand and engage with the content.)

Overcoming Challenges in Special Education Placement and Resource Provision

One key challenge is the decision-making process regarding whether to place students in special education (SPED) classrooms or mainstream classrooms. This decision requires careful consideration of each student's individual needs, learning style, and level of support required to thrive academically. Additionally, ensuring that there are sufficient resources available for mainstream classrooms is crucial, regardless of whether the student with special educational needs is placed there.

Extraordinary (pseudonym) challenges the Department of Education (DepEd) to allocate resources specifically tailored for learners with special educational needs, prioritizing their unique requirements. Placing these learners in classes where they are the central focus could be advantageous, ensuring that their skills and learning receive the necessary attention without being overshadowed by other students. This is evidenced by her statement that says:

“Siguro the DepEd will provide resources na intended jud para sa ilaha nga mga learners kanang tagaan jud sila ug priority, cater man pud sila ilahang mga needs pero mas gwapo jud tong kanang sila jud ilahang kanang dili sila ma sagol sa lain na mga bata aron ma hatagan siya ug attention kung mas focus lang gyud sa ilaha.” (IDI-05)

(Perhaps the Department of Education (DepEd) will provide resources specifically intended for learners with special needs, ensuring they are given priority and their needs are addressed. It would be even better if these learners are placed in classes where they are the main focus, not getting mixed in with other children, so that they can receive the attention they need when the focus is solely on them.)

It was revealed that Star (pseudonym) emphasizes the disparity in support and resources for students with special needs in mainstream versus Special Education classes. While SPED teachers excel in assisting these students, access to advanced tools like technology may be limited. This underscores the importance of ensuring equitable access to resources for all students, regardless of their educational setting. She said:

“Sa ako man gung nakita no, dili jud kaayo mahatagan ug kanang pag tagad kaayo jud bitaw ang mga students with special educational needs if naa sila sa mainstream gali kaysa naa jud sila didto sa SPED kay syempre mga expert na man jud mga maistra didto unsaon sila pag handle unya I think dili pa sab ing ana ka kuan gyud ang mga resources bitaw nato like parehas sa uban nasod.” (IDI-06)

(In my observation, students with special educational needs may not receive the precise attention they require when they are in mainstream classes compared to being in a Special Education (SPED) setting. In SPED, teachers are experts in handling their needs, which might not be the case in mainstream classes. Additionally, I believe our resources may not be as comprehensive compared to those in other countries.)

Bridging the Role of School Psychologists and Medical Professionals

School psychologists play a vital role in identifying learning difficulties and designing interventions within an educational context. On the other hand, medical professionals bring solid expertise to diagnose underlying health issues affecting the child's development. By fostering collaboration, school psychologists and medical professionals can create a holistic approach to support the child's well-being and academic progress. Prioritizing a medical evaluation ensures that any underlying health concerns impacting speech development are addressed effectively.

The priority is to have the child assessed by a doctor, with the option of mainstream schooling if the child can cope, or special education (SPED) support if needed. The assessment revealed delays in speech development for the child, indicating a need for further attention and intervention to address these delays effectively. Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“I prioritize sila nga naa gyud doctor na mo kuan sa ilaha ba, pero ok ra gud if kaya lang sa bata ba nga sa mainstream siya, ok ra pero ug dili pa kaya pero hinoon naa na may mga SPED teacher. Through assessment ang kuan diri kanang late development sa speech nila,

delayed sila.” (IDI-05)

(Prioritize having them evaluated by a doctor, but it is fine if the child can manage in a mainstream setting; however, if not, there are SPED teachers available. Through assessment, it was identified that there are delays in speech development for the child.)

Enhancing Inclusive Education Through Teacher Training and Support Programs

Teacher training programs by the DepEd are vital for preparing mainstream teachers to assist students moving from SPED to graded classrooms. They bridge the gap between different learning environments, ensuring a seamless transition for diverse learners. These programs help teachers comprehend the challenges and strengths of students from SPED, fostering inclusivity and support in the educational setting.

DEPED offers training sessions to help educators bridge the transition of students from special education non-graded settings to graded classrooms. These programs aim to equip teachers with the knowledge and skills needed to facilitate a smooth transition for students with diverse learning needs. By enhancing teacher understanding of the transition process, these training initiatives play a crucial role in promoting inclusive education in mainstream classrooms. Extraordinary stated:

“DEPED conduct mga trainings about how to kanang bridging? gani kuan mura bag gikan ang bata sa SPED kanang non-graded I balhin na siya ug graded so ing ana siya kanang naa man puy gina conduct ang Deped nga ing-ana ginatabangan pud.” (IDI-05)

(DEPED conducts training sessions on how to effectively bridge the transition of students from special education (SPED) non-graded settings to graded classrooms. These training programs assist teachers in understanding the process of transitioning students and provide support to ensure a smooth adjustment for students with diverse learning needs.)

Moreover, Star (pseudonym) mentions the occurrence of seminars and training sessions are held to advance their professional development. These opportunities serve as avenues for reinforcing key learnings from seminars attended by Special Education (SPED) teachers, enabling them to benefit from the expertise shared. They promote a culture of collaborative learning and continuous improvement in inclusive education practices. She stated:

“Naa man sad mi mga seminars na mga mahitabo pud so naay mga trainings na mga pahitaboon then naa sad tong I re-echo tong mga seminars na nakuan sa mga SPED teachers tas I share sab sa amo.” (IDI-06)

(We also have seminars and trainings that take place, where we re-echo the lessons learned from SPED teachers' seminars and share it with us.)

Academic and Behavioral Progress Through a Supportive Learning Environment

The child's significant progress, transitioning from struggling with copying sentences and phrases to being able to write paragraphs and exhibit improved behavior, reflects a remarkable journey of growth and development. Overall, the child's progress in both academic and behavioral aspects underscores the positive impact of a supportive learning environment on their overall development and achievement.

Extraordinary (pseudonym) noted a gradual transformation in the student with autism, observing notable advancements from the beginning and until almost at the end of the semester. This progress was attributed to providing a nurturing environment that allowed the student to freely express their inner thoughts and emotions. She stated:

“Mo participate jud siya na bata ang iyahang improvements is kuan siya from 1st kay naa man jud siyay hard time, pero pagka last quarter kanang mag improve man jud siya. Dako siya ug improvements sa behavior niya ug sa academics.” (IDI-05)

(The child actively participates, showing significant improvements from the first quarter where they faced challenges, but by the last quarter, there is noticeable progress. There have been marked improvements in both their behavior and academic performance.)

Cross-Case Analysis

This single-case study focused on three (3) experienced female teachers with a Bachelor's degree in Elementary Education who each had at least ten years of teaching experience. These teachers had a student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in their mainstream classroom, making them the central focus of the study. A total of three (3) informants was engaged to provide responses to specific questions that the study aimed to address.

The three participants in this study were qualified and experienced teachers who brought valuable insights to the research. Their expertise and firsthand experiences in teaching students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in a mainstream classroom made them invaluable contributors.

By tapping into their knowledge and experiences, the study developed a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced and effective strategies employed in teaching students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in a mainstream educational environment. Their perspectives provided valuable insights into the unique dynamics and approaches needed to support the learning and development of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) within an inclusive classroom.

Research Question No. 1: What are the unique teaching styles and strategies of the teachers teaching students with special educational needs?

This question focuses on the distinctive teaching styles and strategies employed by teachers in their approach to students with Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) within their classrooms. After analyzing the responses of the three participants, the researcher identified five prominent themes that emerged are: individualized instruction, utilizing manipulative objects, balancing technology and traditional approaches, positive reinforcement, and cultivating a sense of belonging. These themes shed light on the unique approaches used by teachers to effectively support students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

Table 2. Unique Teaching Styles and Strategies of the Teachers Teaching Students with Special Educational Needs

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Individualized Instruction	<p>“He is really different. His activities are unique, and I engage with him one-on-one at the table.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“I can see that (student with autism) engages in different activities, sometimes ma’am provides him with activities to do at home.” - IDI-02</p> <p>“He tends to work more individually and is not yet capable of integrating with a regular class that requires serious, intense brainstorming and collaboration of ideas. He just cannot do that. So, if given a chance, he leans more towards art works like painting, coloring, and using manipulative objects. When it comes to numbers or numeracy, he might even collect popsicle sticks or roll dice just to entertain himself.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“It is really difficult if they are not being separated because most of the time they cannot keep up with the other students. So, the strategy for them is to include them and give them activities that are suitable for them and at the same time engaging.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“Every learner indeed has a unique learning style; they require differentiated activities. From what I have observed, they tend to prefer video lessons, especially interactive ones. Their activities are customized; sometimes, they ask, ‘Teacher, can I draw?’ instead of writing for an activity. In response, we accommodate their preferences by allowing them to engage in activities they enjoy.” - IDI-05</p>
Utilizing Manipulative objects	<p>“They just need to have those play areas, those manipulative toys, those manipulative objects that are specifically for them, like building bricks.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“More on art works like paintings, colors, manipulative objects, and for numeracy, using popsicle sticks or dice to entertain him.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“Children with autism respond well to manipulatives. They are not really keen on just being told; they prefer interactive activities like games, playing, exploring colors, and using real objects.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“Everyone loves games, especially students with special educational needs. They enjoy playing and prefer it over writing. Using manipulative objects is what I apply.” - IDI-05</p> <p>“It is really beneficial for children with autism to engage with manipulative objects that they can hold and play with. It brings them joy and, at the same time, helps them learn.” - IDI-06</p>
Balancing Technology and Traditional Approaches	<p>“They use only a TV and a laptop in their classes, still using semi PowerPoint presentations, but with a mix of flashing letters. After story-telling, they use the laptop to show videos. Regarding the technology, they use, I do not really focus on enhancing it, maybe just by 50% because I still assist them.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“With the simple technology, they only use a TV and PowerPoint presentations for viewing purposes. The students do not manipulate the laptop themselves; it is solely used by the teacher. So, the technology they use is limited to PowerPoint slides.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“To enhance the learning experience of students with special educational needs, PowerPoint presentations should be attractive to engage their interest. For example, incorporating alphabet songs and dancing letters can captivate their attention. As a teacher, it is important to create interactive activities where they can actively participate alongside their peers. The presentation should be visually appealing, although it may not always be feasible due to the effort required, but the teacher strives to ensure effective learning.” - IDI-05</p>
Positive Reinforcement	<p>“I make sure to praise them because it is important to acknowledge their actions. Very good, let us applaud them. They become very happy and proud of themselves when they hear ‘oh, I am actually very good’. I just put three stars on their work if they draw really nicely.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“When he comes home from school, he tells me that his notebook seems to be filled with stars, even though he is not very good at writing yet. I encourage him by saying, ‘Good job, keep up the good work in school.’ - IDI-02</p> <p>“Specifically, I have not used positive reinforcement much because the student’s behavior is mainly sleeping. Their behavior is consistently sleeping during class. So, positive reinforcement is not only for students with special educational needs but also for those who are typically developing. By praising him with ‘very good,’ that is his basic form of positive reinforcement that can work for him.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“By telling ‘wow, good job!’ sometimes I also have candies for them to encourage participation.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“I sometimes use verbal praise like ‘Good job!’, ‘Well done!’, and ‘Very good!’. There are also times when I give non-verbal cues like high-fives, which they really enjoy because it signifies appreciation. If they respond well, I give them a thumbs up. Sometimes, I prepare candies and ask, ‘Who wants candy/chocolates?’ I also use stars and smiley faces as rewards, which they really like.” - IDI-05</p> <p>“Yes, children really feel happy when you say ‘wow, good job’ or something similar, and when they respond, if you emphasize and give weight to their answer, they will like that.” - IDI-06</p>
Cultivating a Sense of Belonging	<p>“It is important for their sympathy towards me that they are not afraid, so from the very beginning, I show them that I am like a mother to them. Then they start crying and saying, ‘love-love, ma’am’. Even though they may not fully understand, I explain to them properly so they can comprehend, as it is not because they are children that they cannot</p>

understand, but when you do a one-on-one conversation with them, they do understand.” - IDI-01

It is difficult being a mother to a child with Autism, but I truly see Ma'am as a good teacher because she supports and teaches my child consistently. - IDI-02

“As an educator, first and foremost, it is important to welcome them. Additionally, we cannot overlook the fact that there are some students who may not fully comprehend the situation of an autistic learner. Therefore, as teachers, it is necessary to help them understand the situation and explain to the students that their situation is different from that of other children.” - IDI-03

“Yes, I agree with her. It is crucial for students with special educational needs like Autism to feel welcome. It is like making them feel that they belong. Sometimes, they just really need someone who understands them, even when they are difficult to deal with.” - IDI-04

“As a teacher, it is my duty to keep my classroom organized then promote a calm and positive environment so that the learner with special educational needs can feel he/she belongs to the class then they should need to feel our love, especially for children with autism, as it is important for them to feel that they are truly loved. That is why I give them hugs.” - IDI-05

“As a co-teacher and friend of ma'am Artist (pseudonym) I've seen her create a positive atmosphere for students with special needs, including those with autism, to feel welcomed and supported”. - IDI-06

Individualized Instruction

The participants in the study highlighted the importance of individualized instruction when teaching students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in a mainstream classroom. They emphasized the need to adapt and modify the learning environment and activities to the learners with special education needs to meet the unique needs of each student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

Abacus (pseudonym) highlighted her approach of delivering personalized instruction by adapting activities to suit the student's behavior and developmental stage. She emphasized the individualized nature of the student's tasks, engaging in direct one-on-one instruction at a designated table. This tailored teaching method allows for focused attention and customized learning experiences that cater to the unique needs and abilities of the student. She said:

“Gina lahi gyud na siya, lahi iyang activity, mag one-on-one mi ana sa table.” (IDI-01)

(He is really different; his activities are unique, and I engage with him one-on-one at the table.)

Violet (pseudonym) further supports Abacus (pseudonym) on the teacher's personalized teaching approach for the student with autism. She values the adaptation of activities to meet the student's needs, even extending tasks for home engagement. This supportive method not only addresses the student's learning style but also promotes growth beyond the classroom. She stated:

“Makita nako nga lahi ang mga activities ni (student with autism) ug kanang gina lahi siya ni ma'am, usahay gali kay ginahatagan ni ma'am ug activity na sa balay buhaton.” (IDI-02)

(I can see that (student with autism) engages in different activities, sometimes ma'am provides him with activities to do at home.)

Additionally, one of the participants emphasized the importance of individualized learning for the student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). They pointed out that the student is more suited to individual work and is not yet capable of joining in the typical class activities that require a lot of brain power and collaboration of ideas. As the participant, known by the pseudonym "Artist," stated:

“More on individual work tapos dili man siya pwede I sagol sa normal class uses brain talaga as in brain jud talaga na collaboration of ideas jud, then he cannot do that, so if ever given the chance more on art works like paintings, colors, manipulative objects and if numbers or numeracy man gani kanang mga popsicle sticks na ihapon ba niya or dices para lang mag entertain sa iyaha.” (IDI-03)

(He tends to work more individually and is not yet capable of integrating with a regular class that requires serious, intense brainstorming and collaboration of ideas. He just cannot do that. So, if given a chance, he leans more towards art works like painting, coloring, and using manipulative objects. When it comes to numbers or numeracy, he might even collect popsicle sticks or roll dice just to entertain himself.)

Bubble (pseudonym) emphasized the challenges faced by students with special needs in keeping up with their classmates. She emphasized the importance of integrating these students and providing customized activities to ensure their active participation and engagement. Bubble stressed the significance of creating a supportive and inclusive. She stated:

“Lisod man gud ug dili sila lahion kay sagaran jud dili mana sila maka sabay sa other students so, ang strategy jud ana nila kay lahion unya hatagan sila ug ilaha nga ka busyhan na activities na kanang sibo pud sa iyaha.” (IDI-04)

(It is really difficult if they are not being separated because most of the time they cannot keep up with the other students. So, the strategy for them is to include them and give them activities that are suitable for them and at the same time engaging.)

Moreover, one of the participant emphasized importance of accommodating the student's individual preferences in the classroom. This strategy acknowledges the diverse learning styles present among students, emphasizing the need for varied instructional approaches to effectively meet their educational needs. Extraordinary (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of personalized instruction tailored

to each student's unique learning style. Extraordinary (pseudonym) said:

“Every learner has a different learning style man jud, they need differentiated activities. for them as I observe they prefer video lessons, mga interactive video lessons ang ilahang ganahan sa klase. Gina lahi ang iyahang activity kato siya, usahay mo ingon siya nga “teacher, can I draw?” instead of writing yung activity “Ok, you can draw” we need to give them sa ilahang gusto.” (IDI-05)

(Every learner indeed has a unique learning style; they require differentiated activities. From what I have observed, they tend to prefer video lessons, especially interactive ones. Their activities are customized; sometimes, they ask, "Teacher, can I draw?" instead of writing for an activity. In response, we accommodate their preferences by allowing them to engage in activities they enjoy.)

Utilizing Manipulative objects

Teaching students with special educational needs, particularly those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), can indeed present unique challenges in a mainstream setting. The participants in the study shared common strategies to address these challenges, such as incorporating manipulative objects to not only entertain but also make the learning process more engaging and enjoyable for the students.

After engaging in discussions with the participant, it was revealed that the participant is in favor in using manipulative objects. By using manipulative objects, educators can create hands-on learning experiences that allow students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) to actively participate and interact with the materials. Abacus (pseudonym) said:

“Kinahanglan na lang ana nila dapat no kanang mag form kanang mga dulaan bitaw mga manipulative toys kanang manipulative objects jud na sa ilaha, mga bricks” (IDI-01)

(They just need to have those play areas, those manipulative toys, those manipulative objects that are specifically for them, like building bricks)

Similarly, as mentioned by Artist (pseudonym), highlighted the importance of art-related activities like paintings, colors, and manipulative objects for students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). He mentioned using popsicle sticks or dice for numeracy activities to keep the students engaged and entertained. Artist (pseudonym) said:

“more on art works like paintings, colors, manipulative objects and if numbers or numeracy man gani kanang mga popsicle sticks na ihapon ba niya or dices para lang mag entertain sa iyaha”. (IDI-03)

(More on art works like paintings, colors, manipulative objects, and for numeracy, using popsicle sticks or dice to entertain him)

Bubble (pseudonym) highlights the effectiveness of incorporating manipulatives to engage children on the autism spectrum, recognizing their inclination towards interactive learning experiences over traditional verbal instructions. She believes that interactive approaches not only enhance their academic progress but also cultivate their social and cognitive skills in a supportive educational setting. She stated:

“Ang effective jud anang mga bata nga naay autism kay mga manipulatives jud. Dili kaayo na sila kuan anang mga more into interaction bitaw mas ganahan mana sila ug mga games, mag dula2 unya mga colors2 then mga realia.” (IDI-04)

(Children with autism respond well to manipulatives. They are not really keen on just being told; they prefer interactive activities like games, playing, exploring colors, and using real objects.)

Moreover, one of the participant pointed out that that students with special educational needs, including those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), often have a preference for games and play-based activities over traditional writing tasks. They highlighted the effectiveness of using manipulative objects in teaching, as it allows for a more interactive and hands-on learning experience. Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“Everyone loves game man jud so especially sa student with special educational needs ganahan kaayo siya ug dula mas ganahan man sila ug play kaysa sa writing. Kanang using mga manipulative objects jud, kana jud ang I apply.” (IDI-05)

(Everyone loves games, especially students with special educational needs. They enjoy playing and prefer it over writing. Using manipulative objects is what I apply.)

As mentioned by Star (pseudonym), providing children with autism manipulative objects that they can hold and play with is incredibly valuable. By interacting with these objects, children with autism can enhance their fine motor skills, cognitive abilities, and overall sensory processing. Not only does it bring them joy, but it also aids in their learning process, making it a beneficial and enjoyable experience for them. She stated:

“Ang bagay jud ana sa mga bata nga naay mga autism bitaw kay kana jung mga manipulative objects na ilahang ma gunitan, ma dula-dulaan. Kay malingaw mana sila pero at the same time kay maka learn sad sila.” (IDI-06)

(It is really beneficial for children with autism to engage with manipulative objects that they can hold and play with. It brings them joy

and, at the same time, helps them learn.)

Balancing Technology and Traditional Approaches

Three participants, Abacus, Artist, and Extraordinary, have implemented a strategy that emphasizes a careful balance between technology and traditional teaching methods in the classroom. While technology offers numerous benefits, it's essential to find the right balance and effectively integrate it with traditional teaching methods to create a well-rounded learning environment that caters to the diverse needs of all students. This strategy recognizes that both technology and traditional approaches have unique strengths and can complement each other effectively.

In the interview, one participant mentioned using technology, specifically TVs and laptops, in their teaching approaches for students with special educational needs. However, Abacus (pseudonym) expressed a different perspective, emphasizing that the main focus should be on developing the students' writing skills rather than relying heavily on technology. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“Naga gamit sila ug tv lang and through laptop na ilang mga klase, semi power point gihapon pero kanang mix na kung unsa lang tong letter kato ra pud ilang I flash ing-ana ba unya pagka human mag story telling sila so syempre mag gamit sila laptop kanang mga videos lang. About anang technology nga ginagamit dili kaayo sila 50% jud nga mo enhance diha kay assisted pa man sila nako.” (IDI-01)

(They use only a TV and a laptop in their classes, still using semi PowerPoint presentations, but with a mix of flashing letters. After story-telling, they use the laptop to show videos. Regarding the technology, they use, I do not really focus on enhancing it, maybe just by 50% because I still assist them)

Additionally, Artist (pseudonym) integrates uncomplicated technology like TVs and PowerPoint presentations solely for observational purposes within the classroom setting. The students are not involved in operating the laptops, as they are managed by the teacher for instructional delivery. The strategic use of PowerPoint slides enhances the educational experience by visually reinforcing key concepts and aiding in the comprehension of lesson materials. She said:

“With the simple technology lang, ano lang man ang ginagamit tv lang, powerpoint by simply by viewing lang gyud sila not to the extent na mag manipulate gali sila ug laptop, for teacher use lang gyud na so ang technology is kanang powerpoint lang, powerpoint slide.” (IDI-03)

(With the simple technology, they only use a TV and PowerPoint presentations for viewing purposes. The students do not manipulate the laptop themselves; it is solely used by the teacher. So, the technology they use is limited to PowerPoint slides.)

Extraordinary (pseudonym) mentioned the need for attractive and interactive presentations, incorporating elements like alphabet songs or dancing letters to engage the students. The teacher strives to make the activities interactive and visually appealing, although they acknowledge that it can be challenging at times. The goal is to create an environment where the student can actively participate alongside their peers. She stated:

“To enhance the learning experience of the student with special educational needs, powerpoint presentation, dapat imong powerpoint presentation attractive kay diha sila malingaw. For example, singing of alphabet songs ganahan siya atong naay mag sayaw2 na mga letters, so as a teacher para maka participate siya kauban sa mga bata nga uban kinahanglan nimo himoon nga interactive ang activity unya ang imohang presentation kinahanglan dapat pina gwapa gyud siya pero usahay dili pud biya sa tanang panahon kay kapoy pud biya pero maningkamot jud kay para maka tuon siya.” (IDI-05)

(To enhance the learning experience of students with special educational needs, PowerPoint presentations should be attractive to engage their interest. For example, incorporating alphabet songs and dancing letters can captivate their attention. As a teacher, it is important to create interactive activities where they can actively participate alongside their peers. The presentation should be visually appealing, although it may not always be feasible due to the effort required, but the teacher strives to ensure effective learning.)

Positive Reinforcement

The participants, Abacus, Violet, Artist, Bubble, Extraordinary, and Star, agreed on the importance of positive reinforcement for students with autism. They recognized its ability to significantly boost engagement and foster a positive learning environment. By consistently rewarding and acknowledging desired behaviors, educators can encourage students with autism to repeat those actions, leading to improved participation and overall classroom success. This strategy ultimately shapes behaviors, builds confidence, and creates a nurturing environment conducive to both academic and personal growth.

During the interview, Abacus (pseudonym) emphasized the role of positive reinforcement in encouraging and reinforcing favorable conduct, contributing to a conducive learning environment. Abacus stressed the importance of utilizing strategies that promote positive behaviors to enhance student engagement and overall academic progress. Abacus (pseudonym) said:

“Daygon nako na sila, dili jud na sila pwede dili ko mo dayeg kay kinahanglan na daygon nimo na sila sa ilahang gi buhat. Very good, palakpakan nato. Lipay na kaayo na sila proud kaayo na sila sa ilahang kaugalingon nga ‘ay very good diay ko’ butangan lang nako ug star naa koy pang tatak diha basta gwapo kaayo mo drawing butangan nako na ug star nga tulo.” (IDI-01)

(I make sure to praise them because it is important to acknowledge their actions. Very good, let us applaud them. They become very happy and proud of themselves when they hear 'oh, I am actually very good. I just put three stars on their work if they draw really nicely.)

Violet (Pseudonym) expressed gratitude for the personalized attention her son receives at school, noting his excitement in sharing about receiving a star from his teacher, Abacus (pseudonym). This positive reinforcement not only motivates him but also enhances his enthusiasm for school. Violet values the supportive environment created by Abacus, which boosts her son's confidence and engagement in learning. She stated:

“Pag mo uli na siya gikan skwelahan mo ingon na siya sa akua nga gi tatakan daw ug stars ang iyahang notebook bisan gud ug wala kaayo nagka dimao kay di pa man gyud kaayo siya kabalo mo sulat pero, akua siya gina ingnan nga “maayo dong, padayon lang sa imong pag skwela.” (IDI-02)

(When he comes home from school, he tells me that his notebook seems to be filled with stars, even though he is not very good at writing yet. I encourage him by saying, 'Good job, keep up the good work in school.)

Artist (pseudonym) focused on the use of positive reinforcement for a specific behavior, in this case, a student who tends to sleep during class. The participant mentioned that positive reinforcement is not only beneficial for students with special needs but can also be applied to typically developing students. By praising and acknowledging the student's attentiveness and participation, the teacher encourages the desired behavior and creates a positive learning environment. She explained:

“Specifically, positive reinforcement is wala kaayo nako nagamit is because iyahang behavior man gud, sleeping lang gyud iyang behavior is always sleep lang gyud during the class so, the positive reinforcement is not only for the student with special educational needs but to those really normal na mga studyante. ‘Very good’, by praising him mao na iyang murag basic lang na positive reinforcement na pwede ra gyud sa iyaha.” (IDI-03)

(Specifically, I have not used positive reinforcement much because the student's behavior is mainly sleeping. Their behavior is consistently sleeping during class. So, positive reinforcement is not only for students with special educational needs but also for those who are typically developing. By praising him with 'very good,' that is his basic form of positive reinforcement that can work for him.)

Bubble (pseudonym) incorporates positive reinforcement strategies in her teaching approach by consistently praising her students for their efforts and achievements. This practice not only boosts their confidence but also fosters a supportive and encouraging learning environment, encouraging continued growth and development. She said:

“By telling “wow, good job!” usahay naa sad koy pa candies sa ilaha para lang gyud nga mo participate. “(IDI-04)

(I often say 'Wow, good job!' and sometimes I even give them candies to encourage them to participate.)

Additionally, the participant shared various ways of providing positive reinforcement, including verbal praise, non-verbal cues like high-fives, and occasional rewards like candies or chocolates. These forms of reinforcement serve as immediate feedback and show appreciation for the students' efforts and achievements. Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“I use sometimes verbal praise like ‘Good job!’, ‘well done’ ‘very good’ then there are times pud na non-verbal ques siya kanang mag high-five mo ganahan kaayo na silag high-five pasabot na appreciate nimo, nakatama ba sila I high-five nimo sila, I thumbs up or sometimes kanang mag prepare ko ug candy ‘who wants candy/chocolates?’ kanang star nga I tatak, mga smiley face mao na sila ilahang ganahan.” (IDI-05)

(I often use verbal praise like 'Good job!', 'Well done!', and 'Very good!'. Sometimes I also use non-verbal cues like high-fives, which they really enjoy because it shows appreciation. If they do well, I give them a thumbs up. Sometimes, I have candy ready and ask, 'Who wants candy/chocolates?' I also use stars and smiley faces as rewards, which they really like.)

As per Star (pseudonym) student derive authentic joy from receiving positive affirmations such as "wow, good job," signifying the impact of verbal praise on their emotional well-being. Moreover, when their contributions are acknowledged with emphasis and significance, it not only amplifies their motivation but also enhances their active engagement in learning activities. She said:

“Oo uy, malipay na man gyud ang mga bata anang mo ingon ka ug “wow, good job” or unsa pa na diha tapos ug mo tubag sila imoha pa jud na hatagan ug emphasis ug kabug-aton ganahan na mana sila ana.” (IDI-06)

(Yes, children really feel happy when you say 'wow, good job' or something similar, and when they respond, if you emphasize and give weight to their answer, they will like that.)

Cultivating a Sense of Belonging

During the interview, Abacus, Violet, Artist, Bubble, Extraordinary, and Star emphasized the paramount importance of creating a safe and supportive space for students with special educational needs. By adopting a nurturing and motherly approach, educators can enhance the sense of belonging and emotional well-being of these students, ultimately fostering a conducive environment for their academic growth and development.

The participant emphasized the need for empathy and understanding from others. Abacus (pseudonym) mentioned the importance of showing motherly care and comforting the students when they feel scared or overwhelmed. By explaining the situation to them in a way they can understand, the participant aims to build a strong connection and trust with the students. She stated:

“Kinahanglan nga ang ilahang sympathy pag tan aw sa akoa is dili sila mahadlok, mao na nga 1st pa lang daan ipakita na nako sa ilaha nga motherly gyud nako sa ilaha. Unya mag hilak-hilak na sila I love nako ‘love-love ma’am bi’, bisan ing ana sila ug buot pero akong gi explain sa ilaha ug tarong nga makasabot sila kay dili man tungod na bata sila di kasabot pero imoha na silang I one-on-one kasabot na sila.” (IDI-01)

(It is important for their sympathy towards me that they are not afraid, so from the very beginning, I show them that I am like a mother to them. Then they start crying and saying, “love-love, ma’am”. Even though they may not fully understand, I explain to them properly so they can comprehend, as it is not because they are children that they cannot understand, but when you do a one-on-one conversation with them, they do understand.)

Moreover, Violet (pseudonym) shared that parenting a child with Autism comes with its share of difficulties, yet she recognizes Abacus (pseudonym)’s unwavering dedication to offering a nurturing educational journey for her child. In her statement, she acknowledges the challenges while appreciating the steadfast support and care provided by Abacus in creating a positive learning environment for her child. She said:

“Lisod mahimong inahan sa usa ka bata nga naay Autism apan nakita jud nako nga maayo nga maistra si ma’am kay kanang... gina suportahan ug gina tudloan ra gyud gihapon niya akong anak.” (IDI-02)

(It is difficult being a mother to a child with Autism, but I truly see Ma’am as a good teacher because she supports and teaches my child consistently.)

Artist (pseudonym) mentioned the role of educators in welcoming and helping other students understand the situation of students with autism. It is crucial to educate and raise awareness among students about the unique circumstances and challenges faced by their classmates with special needs. This fosters empathy, acceptance, and a sense of belonging within the classroom. She explained:

“As an educator, first is kailangan I welcome siya and aside from that dili man jud siya malikayan nga there are some students nga who really does not understand the situation of the autistic learner so as a teacher there is a need for them to let them understand the situation so, ipaunawa sa mga bata nga ang situation nila ay kakaiba kaysa sa situation nang isang bata.” (IDI-03)

(As an educator, first and foremost, it is important to welcome them. Additionally, we cannot overlook the fact that there are some students who may not fully comprehend the situation of an autistic learner. Therefore, as teachers, it is necessary to help them understand the situation and explain to the students that their situation is different from that of other children.)

Recognizing the importance of establishing a warm and inclusive environment for students with special educational needs, particularly those with Autism, holds significant resonance. It is vital to communicate to these students that they are integral members of the classroom, nurturing feelings of acceptance and ease. Bubble (pseudonym) emphasizes the significance of creating a supportive and inclusive atmosphere where every student feels valued and embraced. She stated:

“Oo, I agree with her. It is crucial really for students with special educational needs like with Autism to make them feel welcome. Kumbaga, ipa feel sab nimo sa ilaha nga belong sila. Sometimes man sab gud need lang gyud pud nila ug someone nga maka sabot sa ilaha bisan lisod sila sabton.” (IDI-04)

(Yes, I agree with her. It is crucial for students with special educational needs like Autism to feel welcome. It is like making them feel that they belong. Sometimes, they just really need someone who understands them, even when they are difficult to deal with.)

Moreover, the participant highlighted the responsibility of the teacher in maintaining an organized and positive classroom environment. Creating a calm and supportive atmosphere helps students with special educational needs feel like they belong. Showing love and care, such as through hugs, reinforces the sense of belonging and creates a safe space for the autistic student to thrive. Extraordinary (pseudonym) states:

“As a teacher, it is my duty to keep my classroom organize then promote a calm and positive environment so that the learner with special educational needs can feel he/she belongs to the class then they should need to feel our love ang bata man gud nga nay autism no kay kanang kinahanglan ma feel nila na naa jud silay love mao na nga imoha sila nga I hug.” (IDI-05)

(As a teacher, it is my duty to keep my classroom organize then promote a calm and positive environment so that the learner with special educational needs can feel he/she belongs to the class then they should need to feel our love, especially for children with autism, as it is important for them to feel that they are truly loved. That is why I give them hugs.)

Additionally, Star (pseudonym) aligns with Artist’s (pseudonym) in creating a positive environment for students with special needs, including those with autism, ensuring they feel welcomed and supported. In her role as a co-teacher and friend, Star (pseudonym) appreciates the inclusive atmosphere maintained by Artist (pseudonym), fostering a sense of belonging and encouragement for all students. She said:

“As a co-teacher and friend of ma’am Artist (pseudonym) nakita jud nako no nga gahimo gyud siya ug positive atmosphere for students with special needs, including those with autism, to feel welcomed and supported.” (IDI-06)

(As a co-teacher and friend of ma’am Artist (pseudonym) I’ve seen her create a positive atmosphere for students with special needs, including those with autism, to feel welcomed and supported.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of teachers when utilizing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs in a classroom?

This question is about the experiences of the participants when utilizing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs in a classroom, teachers have various lived experiences that shape their approach and impact their effectiveness. This includes the experiences, challenges, struggle, difficulties that can vary depending on the specific needs of the students, the resources available, and the support provided by the school and community. The following themes are: managing students behavior, lack of student participation, lack of training and support.

Table 3. Lived Experiences of Teachers when Utilizing Teaching Strategies for Students with Special Educational Needs

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Managing Students Behavior	<p>“One of the challenges I face with the student is their inability to speak. In my class, they often cry, making it difficult for me to handle.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“I do not know why that child cries excessively, it is really too much. I feel embarrassed because he cries a lot in the classroom, so I sometimes just let him go. The teacher would say, 'Just go to your mom, stop crying, okay?'" - IDI-02</p> <p>“When he has tantrums, even I cannot help him. I try to calm him down by saying 'relax, relax' and comforting him. For example, if he complains of a headache during a tantrum, I massage his head to provide relief because he hurts his head during the tantrum. I also instruct his classmates to hold his hands to prevent him from banging his head, as his head tends to shake during the tantrum.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“It is really challenging to handle them, especially when they become unruly and disruptive in class. You have to calm them down properly, talk to them, reassure them that everything is okay, and ask them to stay put.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“When he has tantrums, he forcefully hits his head on the floor, and it can be quite alarming because he does it with great intensity when he does not get what he wants. In such situations, it is important not to get angry but to calm him down. I hug him tightly, even if he tries to push me away.” - IDI-05</p> <p>We might find it challenging to deal with their behavior in school, but imagine the parents and family members who deal with the child's tantrums and behavior every day. - IDI-06</p>
Lack of Student Participation	<p>“One of the challenges I face with the student is their lack of verbal response. They remain focused on me, but they do not speak even when I try to engage them individually. When I provide one-on-one attention, they stay focused on me during activities, but they do not raise their hand to participate.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“They are not participative throughout the entire duration of their time in class. They often sleep and rarely speak up or engage in activities.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“Some students with autism may sometimes appear noisy, but that student is different, he is quiet and reserved. I have observed that he do not engage much in interactions.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“For children with special educational needs, they are not very attentive and do not actively participate because they are not easily attracted or engaged. It is crucial to find ways to capture their interest and make the lesson attractive to them. Once they are attracted to the lesson, they will actively participate.” - IDI-05</p> <p>“Sometimes he does not speak much because they say children with autism also have difficulties in their communication. They may struggle to express their thoughts, so maybe that is why he does not participate much in class.” - IDI-06</p>
Lack of Training and Support	<p>“We are really lacking support here and then the SPED program does not always have students because it is based on a schedule. Their toys/manipulative objects are very nice, I also wanted to borrow it.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“We don't have any training as teachers, especially not for special education. We were just thrown into this, figuring it out as we go along, trying different strategies and learning through trial and error.” - IDI-03</p> <p>Yes, sometimes I also think that it is challenging, especially because we are more accustomed to mainstream settings we do not say that there is a one-size-fits-all approach. However, I feel that we may not have enough expertise since handling students with specialized needs requires specialized training in special education. We are not adequately trained and skilled to manage students like that. - IDI-04</p> <p>“It is difficult for me in my role because sometimes I struggle to understand them at first, so it is necessary for me to study for them.” - IDI-05</p>

Managing Students Behavior

One of the significant challenges that teachers face when working with student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is managing their behavior. These students may exhibit a wide range of behaviors that can be disruptive, challenging, or even potentially harmful to themselves or others. Teachers often find it difficult to understand the underlying causes of these behaviors and may struggle to find effective strategies to address them.

In the interview, the participant expressed the difficulty of dealing with a non-verbal student who does not communicate. This can present a significant challenge in understanding the student's needs and addressing their behavior effectively. It requires the teacher to

find alternative methods of communication and employ patience and creativity to engage the student. Abacus (pseudonym) said:

“Ang lisdan lang gyud nako sa bata kanang dili mo tingog. Sa akong klase mag hilak2 gali na siya mag lisod na ko.” (IDI-01)

(One of the challenges I face with the student is their inability to speak. In my class, they often cry, making it difficult for me to handle)

The child's excessive crying poses a significant challenge for the teacher, leading to moments of discomfort and potential distraction to class. In response, the teacher occasionally directs the child to his mother, urging him to stop crying. Violet (pseudonym) portrays the complexity of managing the child's emotional outbursts, highlighting the teacher's efforts to navigate these situations while maintaining a conducive learning atmosphere for all students. This is expressed by Violet (pseudonym):

“Ambot anang bataa sobra gyud ka hilakon mamahon kaayo, maulaw na lang ko kay ma'am kay sige hilak sa classroom maong pagawson na lang na siya usahay. Mo ingon si ma'am nga "didto na lang sa ka sa imong mama kaw, ayaw na hilak ha.” (IDI-02)

(I am really at a loss as to why that child cries so much. It is just too much. I feel embarrassed because he cries so often in the classroom, so sometimes I just let him go. The teacher usually says, "Just go to your mom, stop crying, okay?)

Artist (pseudonym) encounters challenges in handling tantrums and emphasized the significance of maintaining composure and offering support to the student in distress. Implementing calming strategies, like gently massaging the student's head when they express discomfort, the teacher strives to provide relief and comfort during difficult moments. She stated:

“Kana lang pag mag tantrum siya kay even me I cannot help him but kanang to say relax lang, relax, I comfort siya like pag mag sakit iyang ulo gina massage nako iyang ulo para ma relieve siya, iya man gung trantrum kay iyang pasakitan iyang ulo. So iyang mga classmate akong ingnon na pugngi iyang kamot kay mabun-og man niya iyang ulo ma uyog gyud iyang ulo.” (IDI-03)

(When he has tantrums, even I cannot help him. I try to calm him down by saying 'relax, relax' and comforting him. For example, if he complains of a headache during a tantrum, I massage his head to provide relief because he hurts his head during the tantrum. I also instruct his classmates to hold his hands to prevent him from banging his head, as his head tends to shake during the tantrum.)

Bubble (pseudonym) expressed the significant difficulty in managing children, particularly when they become unruly and disruptive in class. Effectively calming them down is essential to regain control and create a conducive learning environment. Bubble emphasized the importance of employing calming techniques and establishing clear boundaries to address unruly behavior and promote a positive classroom atmosphere. She stated:

“Lisod jud na sila I handle labi na ug mag wild na bitaw na sila kay grabe jud kalabad sa klase need na sad na nimo sila tarong tarongon ug storya unya pahilomon ingnon na okay ra na, pag puyo ra diha.” (IDI-04)

(It is really challenging to handle them, especially when they become unruly and disruptive in class. You have to calm them down properly, talk to them, reassure them that everything is okay, and ask them to stay put.)

Similarly, Extraordinary (pseudonym) shared the experience of a student who exhibits intense tantrums, including hitting their head on the floor. Managing such behavior can be challenging and potentially dangerous. The participant emphasized the need to remain calm and not get angry. Instead, they recommended hugging the student to provide comfort and help them calm down. She expressed:

“Pag mag tantrums siya kay I pakog-pakog niya iyang ulo sa semento unya ikaw na ang mahadlok kay ikusog gyud niya pag dili ma kuha iyang gusto so ang mahitabo kanang dili na ka masuko imoha siyang pakalmahon, I hug gyud nimo siya sumbag sumbagon pa jud ka ana niya.” (IDI-05)

(When he has tantrums, he forcefully hits his head on the floor, and it can be quite alarming because he does it with great intensity when he does not get what he wants. In such situations, it is important not to get angry but to calm him down. I hug him tightly, even if he tries to push me away)

As highlighted by Star (pseudonym), the ongoing dedication and patience that parents and family members must uphold when addressing a child's tantrums and behavior consistently every day. She underscored the necessity of maintaining a supportive and understanding approach to effectively manage and navigate challenging situations. She said:

“Mag lisod na man gali ta no ug deal sa ilahang behavior in school, unsa na lang ang ginikanan ug pamilya ana nga bata nga everyday jud nila gina deal ang mga tantrums ug behavior sa bata.” (IDI-06)

(We might find it challenging to deal with their behavior in school, but imagine the parents and family members who deal with the child's tantrums and behavior every day.)

Lack of Student Participation

Abacus, Violet, Artist, Bubble, Extraordinary, and Star all shared a common challenge when working with students with special educational needs: limited student participation in classroom activities. This could manifest in various ways, such as students being non-verbal, unresponsive, or simply disengaged during lessons. This lack of engagement can be frustrating for educators, as they strive

to create an inclusive and interactive learning environment for all students.

The participants mentioned the difficulty of getting a non-verbal student to actively participate. Despite one-on-one attention, the student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) remains silent and lack focus on the teacher. This lack of verbal response makes it challenging to gauge their understanding and involve them in activities. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“Ang lisdan lang gyud nako sa bata kanang dili mo tingog, sige lang jud siya ug tutok sa imoha dili siya mo tingog bisan pa ug akoa na siyang isa-isahon, I one-on-one mo tutok ra gyud na siya sa imoha mag activity na mi dinhi dili mana siya mag taas sa iyang kamot.” (IDI-01))

(One of the challenges I face with the student is their lack of verbal response. They remain focused on me, but they do not speak even when I try to engage them individually. When I provide one-on-one attention, they stay focused on me during activities, but they do not raise their hand to participate.)

In addition, the student of Artist (pseudonym) with special educational needs displays consistent non-participation and a tendency to fall asleep during class sessions. This lack of engagement poses a challenge for teachers, impeding the student's educational advancement and restricting their opportunities for social interaction with classmates. She explained:

“Dili jud siya participative for the whole duration sa iyang time ano lang jud siya sleep jud siya, ano wala jud siya seldom lang siya mo tingog.” (IDI-03)

(They are not participative throughout the entire duration of their time in class. They often sleep and rarely speak up or engage in activities.)

Bubble (pseudonym) pointed out that although some students with autism may exhibit loud behavior, there are exceptions. In the case she mentioned, this particular student does not actively engage in interactions. Bubble highlighted the unique communication challenges faced by this student, emphasizing the importance of understanding individual differences. She said:

“naay uban na mga autism student na sabaan pero kato man gud siya na student kay kanang hilomon then nabantayan sab nako na wala kaayo siyay interaction bitaw.” (IDI-04)

(Some students with autism may sometimes appear noisy, but that student is different, he is quiet and reserved. I have observed that he do not engage much in interactions.)

Moreover, Extraordinary (pseudonym) emphasized importance of innovative approaches to captivate and engage students with special educational needs. By crafting activities that resonate with their interests and motivations, educators can cultivate a learning environment that encourages active participation. When students are genuinely intrigued by the lesson content, they are more inclined to participate actively. She stated:

“For children with special educational needs dili kaayo na siya attentive, dili siya mo participate kay dili man siya ma attract kinahanglan gyud niya kay kanang ma attract jud para mo participate jud siya, once na attracted siya sa imong lesson mo participate siya.” (IDI-05)

(For children with special educational needs, they are not very attentive and do not actively participate because they are not easily attracted or engaged. It is crucial to find ways to capture their interest and make the lesson attractive to them. Once they are attracted to the lesson, they will actively participate.)

In addition, Star (pseudonym) shared that individuals with autism may encounter challenges in verbal communication, impacting their ability to express themselves effectively. This difficulty could lead to reduced participation in class discussions or activities. Understanding and accommodating these communication barriers are essential to support their engagement and learning experience. She stated:

“Dili man gud kaayo na siya mo tingog kay ana pa sila kana dawng mga bata nga naay autism kay naa na sab silay difficulties sa ilang pag storya bitaw na kanang dili sila maka express sa ilang gina bati so maybe that is why dili kaayo siya mo tubag sa klase.” (IDI-06)

(Sometimes he does not speak much because they say children with autism also have difficulties in their communication. They may struggle to express their thoughts, so maybe that is why he does not participate much in class.)

Lack of Training and Support

The absence of adequate training and support is evident, as shared by Abacus, Artist, Bubble, and Extraordinary, posing a significant challenge in effectively addressing the diverse needs of students with special educational needs, such as those with autism. Access to resources and guidance is vital to ensure the delivery of quality education to these students. Recognizing this, educational institutions must prioritize investing in training and resources to empower teachers in fulfilling their roles effectively within the classroom setting.

Abacus (pseudonym) expresses a lack of support in their setting and highlights the intermittent presence of students in the Special Education (SPED) program due to scheduled sessions. She reflects the challenges faced in maintaining consistent student attendance

in the SPED program and the speaker's interest in the engaging resources available for students. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“Kulang gyud mi diri ug support unya ang SPED dili biya siya kanunay naay studyante kay schedule ra na siya, mga gwapo kaayo sila ug dulaan lami kaayo ba manghuram.” (IDI-01)

(We are really lacking support here and then the SPED program does not always have students because it is based on a schedule. Their toys/manipulative objects are very nice, I also wanted to borrow it.)

Artist (pseudonym) expressed her frustrations about the lack of training as she is not a specialized SPED teacher who is experienced in handling students with special educational needs. She shared that the strategies she uses in her classroom are all based on trial and error. It can be challenging for her to navigate the unique needs of her students without proper training and guidance. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“Tapos wala sab mi training as teacher nga dili mga sped teacher, wala pud miy training ana amoa lang jud nahulog ra mi nga tagna2 ani.” (IDI-03)

We also did not receive any training as teachers who are not specialized in SPED. We did not have any training specifically for that, we just fell into this role without any prior knowledge.”

Bubble (pseudonym) acknowledges the challenges of integrating students with special needs into mainstream environments and highlights the importance of specialized training in special education. She reflects on the limitations of a one-size-fits-all approach in addressing the diverse learning needs of these students. Bubble expresses a sense of inadequacy in handling students with specialized needs due to the lack of training and skills in special education, emphasizing the necessity for specialized expertise in supporting these students effectively. She expressed:

“Yes, usahay maka ingon sab ko uy na kanang lisod siya labi na kay kanang mas sanay mi nga mainstream biya no wala man sab ta ga kuan ug klase na one-size-fits-all pero man gud mura man ug feel nako dili kaayo mi enough guro para sa mga bata na ing ana kay specialization man gud na sa sped no then kami, we are not trained and skilled to handle students like that.” (IDI-04)

(Yes, sometimes I also think that it is challenging, especially because we are more accustomed to mainstream settings we do not say that there is a one-size-fits-all approach. However, I feel that we may not have enough expertise since handling students with specialized needs requires specialized training in special education. We are not adequately trained and skilled to manage students like that.)

Furthermore, Extraordinary (pseudonym) shared her struggles in dealing with students with special educational needs, particularly a student with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). She had a hard time understanding the student because it was unusual for her, so she needed time to study the behavior and learn how to effectively deal with the student. Extraordinary (pseudonym) said:

“Lisod siya sa akong part kay usahay kay dili ka maka sabot pag pirmero so kailangan jud ka mag study para sa ilaha.” (IDI-05)

(It is difficult for me in my role because sometimes I struggle to understand them at first, so it is necessary for me to study for them.)

Research Question No. 3: How did the teachers cope with the challenges faced in implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs?

In the third question, participants were asked about their coping strategies for the challenges they faced in implementing teaching strategies for students with special educational needs. Thematic analysis of their responses revealed four main coping mechanisms: managing stress and frustration, collaboration with other educators, relying on family as a support system and clear communication and simplified language.

Table 4. *Coping Mechanism of Teachers when Utilizing Teaching Strategies for Students with Special Educational Needs*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Managing Stress and Frustration	<p>“As a teacher, it is important not to get stressed but rather provide the student with separate activities. It is not about letting yourself become stressed by the child, but rather understanding their ways and what they can learn, even if it is just a little.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“Sometimes, I cannot avoid feeling frustrated by his stubbornness, but then I remind myself that he is different from others, and I should be the one to understand him because I am his mother.” - IDI-02</p> <p>“For adjustments, I go with the flow and ride on the student's behavior. I adapt my approach based on their behavior, but overall, the adjustment involves understanding their situation more.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“Positive communication with colleagues and sharing experiences, for example during break time, lunchtime, or before going home when there is still time to chat, can help alleviate stress. It is important not to take things too seriously because we are the ones who will end up being stressed.” - IDI-05</p>
Collaboration with Other Educators	<p>“We have the Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation (MPRE) where we attend seminars. If a SPED teacher has attended a seminar, they would share and re-echo the knowledge gained, especially in areas such as Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) and Lower Order Thinking Skills (LOTS).” - IDI-01</p> <p>“Of course, the Department of Education (DepEd) has Special Education (SPED) teachers assigned to cater to the needs of students with special educational needs. This is a great help for the teachers because DepEd itself ensures that there are teachers specifically designated and knowledgeable in working with these children.” - IDI-03</p>

Relying on Family as a Support System	<p>“It is good to have someone you can lean on. In teaching, it is crucial not to be hesitant and to ask questions to experts like special education teachers.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“I usually seek advice from our master teachers, especially from SPED teachers, because they have received training on how to handle such situations. It is better not to rely solely on our own opinions; we can search for information, but it is even better to receive advice from those with experience. Yes, during meetings with the principal, we can raise our concerns.” - IDI-05</p> <p>“I advised the mother not to let the child have frequent absences because it might hinder their progress and they might miss out on important learning opportunities.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“At times, either I or her older sister would accompany her to school since her sister is already in Grade 6 and their classrooms are close by. Additionally, the older sibling occasionally assists her in learning how to read and write under parental guidance.” - IDI-02</p> <p>“Parental involvement is crucial, and parents should not be in-denial about their child's unique needs. Some parents may struggle with being open-minded, but in the case of this particular child, his mother is very understanding and accepting, which greatly helps in supporting the child.” - IDI-05</p> <p>“The primary support for teachers is really the family, especially the parents or guardians. They are the ones who are with the child from day one, so they know and understand them the most. Our role is to assist, guide, and educate them on how to become better individual.” - IDI-06</p>
Clear Communication and Simplified Language	<p>“With the simpler activities provided, I let him participate in group activities that he is capable of doing. However, if he does not feel like participating at a certain time, I do not force him.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“Yes, they should no longer be given overly difficult activities so they can better understand and answer what you ask them to do.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“I think it is important to modify the instructions and make them clear and simple so that they can understand them right away. If you give them instructions that are too long and complicated, they may not be able to understand. So, it is better to keep the instructions simple and clear.” - IDI-05</p> <p>“You do not have to make things complicated for them. You need to understand their level of learning so that as a teacher, you can assess that this might be too advanced for them because it is too complex. My strategy is to adjust it according to their level.” - IDI-06</p>

Managing Stress and Frustration

During challenging moments, teachers utilized coping strategies to manage stress and frustration when working with students with special needs. They recognized the significance of not becoming overwhelmed or stressed by the students' behavior. Instead, they focused on engaging the students in separate activities, adapting their expectations, and approaching each situation with empathy and patience.

Abacus (pseudonym) expressed the importance of not letting the student's behavior cause stress but rather providing individualized activities and understanding the student's unique way of communicating. This approach helped them avoid personal stress and focus on meeting the student's specific needs. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“As a teacher, kanang dili lang gyud ma stress hatagan na lang gyud ug separate activity ang bata, dili lang gyud nimo ibutang imong kaugalingon nga ma stress jud ka anang bataa, so dili stress imong hunahunaon kundili ang iyahang pamaagi unsa ning bataa nga naay mabal-an bisan gamay.” (IDI-01)

(As a teacher, it is important not to get stressed but rather provide the student with separate activities. It is not about letting yourself become stressed by the child, but rather understanding their ways and what they can learn, even if it is just a little.)

In the interview, Violet (pseudonym) disclosed that she also experiences frustration and stress. They remind themselves that the child's behaviors are distinct from others and emphasize the need to provide understanding and support as a parent. By reframing the situation and considering the child's individuality, the speaker aims to approach interactions with empathy and patience. She stated:

“Usahay dili gyud malikayan nga saputon ko sa iyahang kagahi ug ulo pero mahuna-hunaan na lang pud nako nga lahi man siya sa uban dapat ako na lang gyud pud ang mo sabot kay ako man iyang mama.” (IDI-02)

(Sometimes, I cannot avoid feeling frustrated by his stubbornness, but then I remind myself that he is different from others, and I should be the one to understand him because I am his mother.)

Also in the interview, another participant emphasize the importance of going with the flow and responding to the student's actions to create a supportive environment. By prioritizing understanding the student's situation, the speaker aims to meet the student's needs effectively, highlighting the significance of flexibility and empathy in supporting the student's learning and well-being. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“For adjustments of course kung ano yung pinapakita niya na behavior kumbaga I just go with the flow; nag ride on lang ko sa iyahang behavior pero so far kanang adjustment is more understanding more sa iyang situation.” (IDI-03)

(For adjustments, I go with the flow and ride on the student's behavior. I adapt my approach based on their behavior, but overall, the adjustment involves understanding their situation more.)

Positive communication and sharing experiences with colleagues were highlighted by another participant as a way to cope with stress. She mentioned taking advantage of break times or meal times to have informal discussions with colleagues, which provided an opportunity to share experiences and support one another. This form of communication and support helped alleviate stress and prevented them from taking things too seriously. Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“Positive communication with colleagues, sharing experiences for example during break time, noon time or before mag uli naa pa may time mag chika-chika then eating, sharing while eating oh diba makawala ug stress. Dili lang gyud nato seryosohon kay na kita ra gihapoy ma konsimisyon.” (IDI-05)

(Positive communication with colleagues and sharing experiences, for example during break time, lunchtime, or before going home when there is still time to chat, can help alleviate stress. It is important not to take things too seriously because we are the ones who will end up being stressed.)

Collaboration with Other Educators

Collaboration among educators emerged as a crucial element in effectively supporting students with autism. Participants emphasized the importance of seeking guidance from specialists, such as special education teachers, to enrich teaching practices and better support students with diverse learning needs. Consulting master teachers, particularly SPED teachers, to gain specialized training and knowledge for effectively handling diverse situations in the classroom was also highlighted as a crucial aspect of supporting students with autism.

In the interview, it was disclosed that Abacus (pseudonym) engages in collaborative efforts with various educators, including the principal, SPED teacher, and co-teachers. Together, they exchange knowledge and expertise, fostering a collaborative environment aimed at enhancing their collective understanding and effectiveness in supporting students. She stated :

Of course, naa na man gyud sa DepEd nang SPED unya naa puy teach na mo cater so it is a great help na for the teacher na si DepEd mismo naay nakatalaga nga teacher na knowledgeable jud sa ing ana na mga bata.” (IDI-01)

(Of course, the Department of Education (DepEd) has Special Education (SPED) teachers assigned to cater to the needs of students with special educational needs. This is a great help for the teachers because DepEd itself ensures that there are teachers specifically designated and knowledgeable in working with these children.)

Moreover, Artist (pseudonym) emphasized the support provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) in terms of having dedicated SPED teachers. They acknowledged the value of having knowledgeable teachers assigned by DepEd to cater specifically to students with special needs. This collaboration between the school and DepEd was seen as a great help for teachers in effectively teaching these students. She stated:

“Naa man mi mag MPRE (Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation) naa mi seminar, parehas anang SPED teacher dinha kung naa na siyay seminar gina re-echo na niya kay kana iyang bata diha halo2 man gud kana pung mga HOTS mga LOTS nga ilang gina seminaran gina re-echo na.” (IDI-03)

(We have the Midyear Performance Review and Evaluation (MPRE) where we attend seminars. If a SPED teacher has attended a seminar, they would share and re-echo the knowledge gained, especially in areas such as Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) and Lower Order Thinking Skills (LOTS).

Bubble (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of having a support system to rely on is invaluable. In the field of teaching, it is essential to overcome any hesitations and seek guidance by posing questions to professionals, such as special education teachers. Utilizing the expertise and experience of specialists can enrich one's teaching practice and enhance the support provided to students with diverse learning needs. She stated:

“It is good to have someone you can lean on to. In teaching, importante jud na dili ta magpa hawd2 unya manguatana jud ta daan sa mga experts like the sped teachers.” (IDI-04)

(It is good to have someone you can lean on. In teaching, it is crucial not to be hesitant and to ask questions to experts like special education teachers.)

Seeking advice and guidance from master teachers was highlighted by Extraordinary (pseudonym). She mentioned the presence of several master teachers in their school, particularly SPED teachers who had specialized training and experience. By consulting these experienced professionals, educators can benefit from specialized training and knowledge in handling diverse situations effectively. Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“I usually seek advice from our master teachers then most especially sa SPED teachers jud kay sila man ang naka skwela ana ug unsaon mas maayo mana nga dili ta mag buot-buot ba pwede gud ta maka search pero mas maayo gyud nang naay maka advise sa imoha kay sila may naay experience. Yes, sa principal kanang mga ing-ana sa mga meetings pwede nimo ma raise ang imohang problema.” (IDI-05)

(I usually seek advice from our master teachers, especially from SPED teachers, because they have received training on how to handle such situations. It is better not to rely solely on our own opinions; we can search for information, but it is even better to receive advice from those with experience. Yes, during meetings with the principal, we can raise our concerns.)

Relying on Family as a Support System

Open communication and collaboration between teachers and families create a consistent support system for students. This partnership helps students overcome challenges and thrive academically and emotionally. The participants recognize families as primary companions who possess a deep understanding of their child's needs, making them invaluable partners in the educational journey.

In the one-on-one interview, Abacus (pseudonym) shared to me the importance of relying on family as a support system, particularly for parents. They highlighted that parents play a crucial role as one of the primary supports in helping teachers navigate any difficulties that may arise. By fostering a strong partnership between teachers and families, students with special educational needs can receive the comprehensive support they need to overcome challenges and thrive academically and emotionally. She said:

“akong gina ingnan ang mama nga ayaw sige pa absena ang bata kay basin matabang pa na nato basin maka balo pa na.” (IDI-01)

(I advised the mother not to let the child have frequent absences because it might hinder their progress and they might miss out on important learning opportunities.)

There are instances when the elder sibling takes on the role of an occasional mentor, imparting lessons on reading and writing under the watchful eye of parental guidance. By engaging in these educational exchanges, siblings not only support each other's learning but also strengthen family bonds through shared academic experiences. Violet (pseudonym) stated:

“Usahay ako o iyang ate mo hatod ana sa iyaha sa skwelahan kay grade 6 na man sad iyang ate ba so I hapit ra siya sa room. Gina tudloan sab usahay ug basa ug sulat sa maguwang.” (IDI-02)

(At times, either I or her older sister would accompany her to school since her sister is already in Grade 6 and their classrooms are close by. Additionally, the older sibling occasionally assists her in learning how to read and write under parental guidance.)

Similarly, Extraordinary (pseudonym) shares the significance of parental involvement and open-mindedness in understanding and accepting their child's unique needs rather than denying them. By acknowledging and embracing their child's individual requirements, parents can provide effective support and nurture a positive learning environment. Extraordinary (pseudonym) expressed:

“Parent’s involvement dapat gyud, sa parent dili siya in denial na ing ana kay naa gyud pud biyay mga mama nga dili ing ana, dili open-minded pero katong bata na kato siya gwapo lang gyud ato iyang nanay mismo open kaayo nga mao nga masabtan jud siya.” (IDI-05)

(Parental involvement is crucial, and parents should not be in-denial about their child's unique needs. Some parents may struggle with being open-minded, but in the case of this particular child, his mother is very understanding and accepting, which greatly helps in supporting the child.)

Similarly, Star (pseudonym) highlights the crucial role of families, particularly parents or guardians, in supporting teachers and students with autism. They emphasize that families are the child's primary companions from day one, possessing a deep understanding of their needs. The speaker's aim is to assist, guide, and educate families on how to nurture and develop children into well-rounded individuals. She said:

“Ang primary jud na maka tabang sa mga teachers no is the family jud, especially the parents or guardians. Sila biya jud ang kauban sa bata day 1 pa lang so sila ang mas nakaila ug nakasabot sa ilaha. So amoa lang pud is to help them, guide and teach them how to become better individuals.” (IDI-06)

(The primary support for teachers is really the family, especially the parents or guardians. They are the ones who are with the child from day one, so they know and understand them the most. Our role is to assist, guide, and educate them on how to become better individual.)

Clear Communication and Simplified Language

One of the ways to cope up with the teaching strategies of teachers teaching students with special educational needs is by providing simpler activities and clear instructions, teachers can create an inclusive learning environment that promotes active participation and understanding. This ensures that students can fully engage in the learning process and achieve their potential. It emphasizes the importance of flexibility and personalized instruction in catering to the unique needs of each student with special educational needs.

Artist (pseudonym) emphasized the significance of offering simplified activities tailored to the student's abilities and facilitating their involvement in suitable group activities. It is essential to respect the student's willingness to participate and avoid coercing them into activities they may not be ready for at that moment. Artist (pseudonym) stated:

“With the simpler activities provided letting him to engage like I apil lang jud siya sa mga group activities yung kaya lang niya pero

pag time na dili siya gusto dili nako siya pugson.” (IDI-03)

(With the simpler activities provided, I let him participate in group activities that he is capable of doing. However, if he does not feel like participating at a certain time, I do not force him.)

Bubble (pseudonym), emphasized the importance of avoiding tasks that are too difficult for students with autism, as this can hinder their understanding and active participation. Simplifying activities can improve students' comprehension of instructions and encourage them to engage more effectively in the learning process. By adapting tasks to students' abilities, educators can enhance learning outcomes and student involvement. She stated:

“Oo, dili na gyud kaayo na sila lisod-lisodon ug mga activities arun masabtan ug ma answeran jud nila ang imong gipabuhat.” (IDI-04)

(Yes, they should no longer be given overly difficult activities so they can better understand and answer what you ask them to do.)

Also, similar to Artist (pseudonym) statement, Extraordinary (pseudonym) also emphasized the need to modify instructions by making them clear and simple. The participant highlighted the importance of using language and instructions that the students can easily understand. By avoiding overly complicated instructions, the students can grasp the tasks more quickly and effectively. She said:

“I think is to modify the instructions, make the instruction clear and simple para maka gets dayun kay ug imoha siyang I taas ra kaayo ug instructions sa ilaha dili mana nila ma (sabtan) so mas maayo gyud tong simple unya clear.” (IDI-05)

(I think it is important to modify the instructions and make them clear and simple so that they can understand them right away. If you give them instructions that are too long and complicated, they may not be able to understand. So, it is better to keep the instructions simple and clear.)

Star (pseudonym) believes that educators need to recognize and adapt to the individual learning styles and needs of each student. By tailoring instruction to their level of understanding, educators can ensure that the material is appropriate and engaging, leading to optimal learning outcomes. This individualized approach fosters a supportive and inclusive learning environment. She said:

“You do not have to make things complicated for them. Kailangan kabalo sab ka sa ilahang level of learning so that ikaw as a teacher maka bana-bana ka nga ay kini dili pa kaayo siya pwede ani kay complex ra kaayo so akong strategy is to adjust it according to their level.” (IDI-06)

(You do not have to make things complicated for them. You need to understand their level of learning so that as a teacher, you can assess that this might be too advanced for them because it is too complex. My strategy is to adjust it according to their level.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of the teachers’ teaching students with special educational needs when using different strategies to cater the needs of the students?

This question is about the insight of the teachers in the challenges, struggles, and difficulties they have experience in teaching students with special educational needs when using different strategies to cater the needs of the students. Also, by exploring the insights gained from these challenges, teachers can continually improve their teaching practices and create an inclusive learning environment that fosters the success and well-being of all students. The following themes were: individualized learning and learning style, inclusive and supportive classroom environment, challenging stigma and promoting acceptance, involvement of school psychologists and training for mainstream teachers.

Table 5. Insights of Teachers when Utilizing Teaching Strategies for Students with Special Educational Needs

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Individualized Learning and Learning Styles	<p>“I cater him on a one-on-one basis because they cannot be mixed with others. I make sure to give him dedicated time, and when he wants to play, I guide him through it. When he writes, I guide him closely so that he can be properly guided.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“One effective strategy may be to allow him to manipulate devices, real objects, to learn how to be independent. For example, teaching him how to organize his belongings, turn on lights, operate televisions, and arrange his things. This strategy is particularly beneficial for individuals with autism, as it promotes lifelong learning and independence. By empowering him to perform daily tasks on his own, he can develop essential life skills and reduce his reliance on constant guidance.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“Using video lessons, differentiated activities, concrete examples that are similar to their experiences, and incorporating manipulative materials and toys can greatly motivate them.” - IDI-05</p>
Inclusive and Supportive Classroom Environment	<p>“From the very first meeting, it is important to create a welcoming aura that makes the student feel comfortable and safe, so they would not be afraid. Building trust is crucial to ensure that the student feels secure and becomes more willing to engage. Once trust is established, the student will be more open and return regularly.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“For me, a rewarding experience would probably be when he feels welcome and does not feel like he is being bullied in the environment.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“In teaching, we encounter diverse learners, so if there is a situation where we have a student with autism, it is crucial to accept and welcome them, making them feel that they belong.” - IDI-04</p>

	“Because I noticed that unlike other children, every time he arrives, he hugs you. He is really sweet, this child. He hugs you, so he really needs to feel that you give him more attention because he is really different, you know.” - IDI-05
Challenging Stigma and Promoting Acceptance	“He is also not accepted into the SPED program, and it is also because I am not a SPED teacher. It feels like it would be an additional burden for me to take on, but it is okay because having autism does not make them bad or attention-seeking, they just need some extra understanding.” - IDI-01 “I suggested that why not place him/her in the Special Education (SPED) program since it is more spacious there, and the children are separated and their needs are specifically catered to. Because if it is just me teaching the regular class, it would be difficult for me to allocate time specifically for him/her, as it would be solely focused on him/her.” - IDI-03
Involvement of School Psychologists	“First, he is really bullied because, of course, he is different, they cannot understand him, and eventually, his classmates understands his situation.” - IDI-05 “It is necessary for the child to be placed in SPED (Special Education), and the SPED teacher refused and told me to wait until Grade 3 for the child to be non-graded. They will just graduate the child in Grade 6 so that they can return to regular schooling.” - IDI-01 “I hope that the Department of Education (DepEd) will provide free assessments to assess all children in school who are identified by the teacher as having potential special needs.” - IDI-03 “Prioritize those (students with special educational needs) to have an access to a doctor. Through assessment, the focus here is on late development of their speech, indicating a delay. There is a recent case of a student who is currently in Grade 2, coming from SPED, but still needs to report to the SPED center at certain days and times for monitoring.” - IDI-05
Training for Mainstream Teachers	“The SPED teacher who attended the seminar shared about what they learned regarding teaching children with autism. They have USBs with videos that they use to share it with us demonstrate different activities specifically designed for children with autism.” - IDI-01 “We are teachers but we have not received training as teachers, especially not as Special Education (SPED) teachers. We also did not receive training for that. We are just left on our own with guesswork.” - IDI-03 “We also do not have much experience in handling such children because we have not encountered a student with autism before, and we also lack the necessary seminars and training. It is like being thrown into a battle without preparation.” - IDI-04 “DEPED conducts training sessions on how to effectively bridge the transition of students from special education (SPED) non-graded settings to graded classrooms. These training programs assist teachers in understanding the process of transitioning students and provide support to ensure a smooth adjustment for students with diverse learning needs.” - IDI-05 “We also have seminars and trainings that take place, where we re-echo the lessons learned from SPED teachers' seminars and share it with us.” - IDI-06

Individualized Learning and Learning Styles

The focus on individualized instruction, designed to meet each student's unique needs, embodies the principles of differentiated instruction, a well-established and effective approach for supporting diverse learners. The participants' recommendations for incorporating hands-on activities, visual aids, and differentiated instruction align with research-supported methods for engaging students with special needs and fostering their learning.

In the interview, the researcher found out that the most efficient way to educate students with special educational needs is through differentiated instruction. Abacus (pseudonym) emphasizes the significance of one-on-one instruction for the student. By providing individualized attention and time, the teacher can tailor their teaching to the specific needs of the student. She stated:

“I cater gyud siya I one-on-one man gud na sila dili pwede sila I halo gyud hatagan jud na nimo sila ug time unya mag dula gali na sila taparan jud na nimo, kung mag suwat taparan gyud na nimo kay aron nga ma guide.” (IDI-01)

(I cater him on a one-on-one basis because they cannot be mixed with others. I make sure to give him dedicated time, and when he wants to play, I guide him through it. When he writes, I guide him closely so that he can be properly guided.)

Moreover, Artist (pseudonym) also highlights An effective strategy involves allowing the individual to interact with real objects and devices to foster independence. This includes teaching tasks like organizing belongings, operating appliances, and arranging personal items. Particularly advantageous for individuals with autism, this strategy promotes lifelong learning, independence, and the development of crucial life skills, ultimately reducing their dependence on continuous assistance. She said:

“One strategy may be effective is letting him manipulate device, realia, real objects how to use halimbawa para magiging independent jud siya kay autistic biya siya how to keep your things, how to turn on lights, how to turn on and off televisions, how to arrange your things, for long life learning gyud niya kay dili biya siya habang buhay naay mag guide sa iya at least one strategy is letting him do things daily na ginagawa.” (IDI-03)

(One effective strategy may be to allow him to manipulate devices, real objects, to learn how to be independent. For example, teaching him how to organize his belongings, turn on lights, operate televisions, and arrange his things. This strategy is particularly beneficial for individuals with autism, as it promotes lifelong learning and independence. By empowering him to perform daily tasks on his own,

he can develop essential life skills and reduce his reliance on constant guidance.)

In addition, Extraordinary (pseudonym) added that the use of video lessons, differentiated activities, and concrete examples is crucial. These strategies cater to the diverse learning styles of students with special educational needs. By incorporating manipulative materials, toys, and experiences that are relatable to the students, teachers create a more engaging and accessible learning environment. She stated:

“Using video lessons, differentiated activities, mga concrete examples mga similar sa ilang experiences kung pwede kanang mga manipulative materials, mga toys mga ing-ana mao nay maka motivate sa ilaha.” (IDI-05)

(Using video lessons, differentiated activities, concrete examples that are similar to their experiences, and incorporating manipulative materials and toys can greatly motivate them.)

Inclusive and Supportive Classroom Environment

Teachers like Abacus (pseudonym), Artist (pseudonym), and Bubble (pseudonym) recognize the importance of creating a welcoming and inclusive learning environment for all students, especially those with Autism. They emphasize the need to build trust, foster a sense of belonging, and cultivate a nurturing atmosphere that is free from bullying or exclusion. By prioritizing acceptance and providing individualized attention, educators can empower students with Autism to feel valued, respected, and comfortable participating in the learning process.

The participant shared that establishing a welcoming and safe environment from the initial encounter is vital to help students feel at ease and unafraid. Building trust is key in fostering a sense of security and encouraging active participation from the student. Once a foundation of trust is laid, the student is more likely to feel comfortable, engage willingly, and return consistently. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“Pag meet pa lang jud nimo sa iyaha dapat ang imong aura mo gaan na ang loob sa bata sa imoha arun ang bata dili bitaw mahadlok. Dapat makuha na nimo ang trust arun dili na siya mahadlok, sunod mag sige na siya ug balik-balik.” (IDI-01)

(From the very first meeting, it is important to create a welcoming aura that makes the student feel comfortable and safe, so they would not be afraid. Building trust is crucial to ensure that the student feels secure and becomes more willing to engage. Once trust is established, the student will be more open and return regularly.)

Similarly, Artist (pseudonym) sees the rewarding experience is when the student feels genuinely welcomed and does not sense any form of bullying in the environment. Creating a safe and inclusive space where the student feels valued and respected is crucial for fostering a positive learning experience. Ensuring that the student feels comfortable and accepted. Artist (pseudonym) states:

“Para sa akoa rewarding experience siguro kanang ma feel welcome lang gihapon siya then dili niya ma feel ang environment nga gi bully siya.” (IDI-03)

(For me, a rewarding experience would probably be when he feels welcome and does not feel like he is being bullied in the environment.)

When faced with diverse learners, such as students with autism, in teaching, it is imperative to prioritize acceptance and create a welcoming environment where they feel included and valued. Ensuring that students with autism feel a sense of belonging contributes to their overall well-being and academic success. Educators can empower these students to thrive and engage effectively in the learning process. Bubble (pseudonym) stated:

“In teaching, we have diverse learners man so if naay situation like ing ani na naa tay student na naay autism, it is crucial to accept and welcome them ipa feel sa ilaha nga belong sila.” (IDI-04)

(In teaching, we encounter diverse learners, so if there is a situation where we have a student with autism, it is crucial to accept and welcome them, making them feel that they belong.)

Furthermore, the other participant highlights the unique behavior of a particular child who consistently shows affection by hugging upon arrival, emphasizing the child's sweet nature. Recognizing this difference, the speaker stresses the importance of providing the child with additional attention to meet their specific needs and make them feel valued and understood. Extraordinary (pseudonym) states:

“Kay nabantayan nako sa ilaha unlike sa other na mga bata kada abot niya, mo hug siya sa imoha, sweet jud siya na bata mo hug siya sa imoha so kinahanglan na ma feel gyud niya nga mo hatag ka sa iyaha ug more attention kay lahi ra jud biya siya no.” (IDI-05)

(Because I noticed that unlike other children, every time he arrives, he hugs you. He is really sweet, this child. He hugs you, so he really needs to feel that you give him more attention because he is really different, you know.)

Challenging Stigma and Promoting Acceptance

Addressing stigma and promoting acceptance is essential in today's society, particularly concerning individuals with special educational

needs like autism. Individuals with autism frequently encounter misunderstandings, discrimination, and challenges within mainstream educational environments. By challenging these stigmas and fostering acceptance, we can create inclusive spaces that support and empower individuals with autism to thrive and succeed.

In the interview, Abacus (pseudonym) expressed her concerns about teaching a student with autism, the child is not included in the Special Education (SPED) program. Despite feeling like taking on this responsibility would be an added challenge, the speaker acknowledges that having autism does not equate to being bad or seeking attention; rather, it signifies a need for additional understanding and support. She stated:

“Dili man pud siya dawaton didto sa SPED gud, mao pud lagi maka ingon pud lagi kay dili man pud ko SPED teacher, murag ma dugang siya nako na trabahoon pero ok ra man pud sa ako nang autism kay dili mana sila badlongon, papansin lang.” (IDI-01)

(He is also not accepted into the SPED program, and it is also because I am not a SPED teacher. It feels like it would be an additional burden for me to take on, but it is okay because having autism does not make them bad or attention-seeking, they just need some extra understanding.)

Similarly, Artist (pseudonym) also proposed the idea of placing the student with autism in a Special Education (SPED) class. She emphasized that the SPED classroom provides a more spacious environment where the student's learning needs can be better accommodated. Artist (pseudonym) shared her personal struggle of teaching the student with autism in a regular classroom setting. She said:

“Gi suggest nako na why not didto siya sa SPED since luag didto sa SPED room tapos ang mga bata kumbaga ma separate gyud siya tapos ma cater gyud iyang needs kay kung ako lang, teaching the normal class murag mag lisod ko ug mag hatag ug time na para sa iyaha na para lang gyud sa iyaha.” (IDI-03)

(I suggested that why not place him/her in the Special Education (SPED) program since it is more spacious there, and the children are separated and their needs are specifically catered to. Because if it is just me teaching the regular class, it would be difficult for me to allocate time specifically for him/her, as it would be solely focused on him/her.)

During the interview, Extraordinary (pseudonym) mentioned that the student with autism initially experienced bullying due to their distinctive behaviors. However, as time progressed, the classmates started to comprehend and accept the student's behavior. This shift in understanding and acceptance highlights the positive impact of awareness. Extraordinary (pseudonym) stated:

“Permero, gina bully gyud siya kay syempre lahi man siya, dili siya makasabot, pagka dugayan na ang iyahang classmate na pud ang nakasabot.” (IDI-05)

(First, he is really bullied because, of course, he is different, they cannot understand him, and eventually, his classmates understands his situation.)

Involvement of School Psychologists

The participants' recommendations align with my study's focus on understanding the needs and challenges faced by teachers of students with special educational needs. Their emphasis on accessible psychological assessments and the need for free evaluations addresses key concerns in my research. Their insights also highlight the crucial role of school psychologists in supporting these students, a theme central to my study's exploration of professional roles.

During the discussions with the participants, one of them, referred to as Abacus (pseudonym) expresses concern, suggesting that a child might be stuck in a non-graded system until reaching Grade 3 and only then being allowed to return to mainstream education. Here, the role of a school psychologist could be critical in assessing the child's capabilities and readiness to transition to a regular class. They could provide recommendations based on the child's cognitive, emotional, and social development. She stated:

“Dapat didto na na siya sa SPED, tapos si SPED teacher dili man pud mo dawad ug dili pa daw mo abot sa grade 3 mahulog na na siya nga non-graded, I graduate na lang jud na nila ug grade 6 usa na siya maka balik balik ug skwela.” (IDI-01)

(It is necessary for the child to be placed in SPED (Special Education), and the SPED teacher refused and told me to wait until Grade 3 for the child to be non-graded. They will just graduate the child in Grade 6 so that they can return to regular schooling.)

Moreover, Artist (pseudonym) suggested offering complimentary assessments to students identified by teachers as potentially requiring special educational support. This approach is vital as not all parents may have the financial resources to pursue evaluations from psychiatrists or medical professionals for their children. By providing free assessments, educators can ensure that all students have equal access to necessary evaluations and support services, regardless of their financial circumstances. Artist (pseudonym) said:

“I hope si DepEd mag hatag siya ug assessment na free na I assess tanang bata sa school na nakitaan lang ni teacher na there is something special needs sa bata..” (IDI-03)

(I hope that the Department of Education (DepEd) will provide free assessments to assess all children in school who are identified by the teacher as having the potential.)

Similarly, as with Extraordinary (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of having a doctor involved in the care of students with special educational needs but also recognizes the value of SPED teachers. It mentions the need for continuous assessment, especially for children with delayed speech development. Here, school psychologists could work in conjunction with speech therapists and SPED teachers to monitor the child's progress and adjust the intervention plan as needed. She stated:

“I prioritize sila nga naa gyuy doctor sa ilaha ba. Through assessment ang kuan diri kanang late development sa speech nila, delayed sila. Naa may bag o nga nag grade 2 na siya karun gikan sa SPED pero pagka grade 2 niya mag report gihapon siya nay adlaw nay oras nga mo adto siya didto para ma monitor siya.” (IDI-05)

(Prioritize those (students with special educational needs) to have an access to a doctor. Through assessment, the focus here is on late development of their speech, indicating a delay. There is a recent case of a student who is currently in Grade 2, coming from SPED, but still needs to report to the SPED center at certain days and times for monitoring.)

Training for Mainstream Teachers

The emphasis on knowledge sharing, such as the practice of re-echoing insights from SPED teachers' seminars, demonstrates the importance of collaborative learning and professional development within the educational system. These insights align with research emphasizing the need for continuous learning and training for educators to effectively support students with special needs, promoting inclusive and equitable learning environments.

In the interview, the participant mentions that the SPED teacher has attended seminars and shares the knowledge gained about working with children with autism. However, teachers in mainstreaming settings only use USBs to show videos and recorded audios from the seminars that the SPED teachers attended to. This highlights the importance of continuous professional development and training for mainstreaming teachers. Abacus (pseudonym) stated:

“Si SPED teacher naa to siyay gi seminaran iya ng I sulti about sa iyang gi seminran sa mga bata nga kanang naay autism. Naa mana silay mga USB ilaha ng ipang show didto ang video kasagaran jud anang mga autism hatagan ra jud na sila ug mga dulaan.” (IDI-01)

(The SPED teacher who attended the seminar shared about what they learned regarding teaching children with autism. They have USBs with videos that they use to share it with us demonstrate different activities specifically designed for children with autism.)

In addition, the researcher also discovered that Artist (pseudonym) lacked the proper knowledge and experience in handling students with autism. Recognizing this, she sought advice from previous teachers who had worked with the student with autism. She inquired about effective strategies for managing his behavior and sought guidance on how to best support his specific needs. She said:

“Teacher man ta so tapos wala sab mi training as teacher nga dili mga sped teacher, wala pud miy training ana amoa lang jud nahulog ra mi nga tagna2.” (IDI-03)

(We are teachers but we have not received training as teachers, especially not as Special Education (SPED) teachers. We also did not receive training for that. We are just left on our own with guesswork.)

Bubble (pseudonym) expresses a lack of experience in handling children with autism due to not having encountered such students before and a shortage of relevant seminars and training. The analogy of being thrown into a battle without preparation highlights the challenges faced by educators when addressing the needs of students with autism without adequate training or resources.. As stated by Bubble (pseudonym):

“Dili man sab gud kaayo mi hawd mo handle ug ing ana na mga bata kay wa miy ka agi pa sukad nga naay studyante nga naay Autism tapos wala sad biya jud enough no nga mga seminars, training para ana kumbaga diretso na mi naa sa gyera nga walay preparation.” (IDI-04)

(We also do not have much experience in handling such children because we have not encountered a student with autism before, and we also lack the necessary seminars and training. It is like being thrown into a battle without preparation.)

These training sessions focus on bridging the gap between non-graded and graded environments, ensuring a smooth transition for students with diverse learning needs. Not only do these programs benefit teachers in understanding the unique challenges and strengths of students coming from SPED programs, but they also facilitate a more inclusive and supportive educational environment. Extraordinary stated:

“DEPED conduct mga trainings about how to kanang bridging2 gani kuan mura bag gikan ang bata sa SPED kanang non-graded I balhin na siya ug graded so ing ana siya kanang naa man puy gina conduct ang Deped nga ing-ana ginatabangan pud.” (IDI-05)

(DEPED conducts training sessions on how to effectively bridge the transition of students from special education (SPED) non-graded settings to graded classrooms. These training programs assist teachers in understanding the process of transitioning students and provide support to ensure a smooth adjustment for students with diverse learning needs.)

Moreover, Star (pseudonym) mentions the presence of seminars and trainings within their setting where they echo the key learnings from seminars attended by Special Education (SPED) teachers and share this knowledge with their colleagues. This practice of re-

echoing and disseminating insights from SPED teachers' seminars highlights a collaborative approach to professional development and knowledge sharing among educators. She stated:

“Naa man sad mi mga seminars na mga mahitabo pud so naay mga trainings na mga pahitaboon then naa sad tong I re-echo tong mga seminars na nakuan sa mga SPED teachers tas I share sab sa amo.” (IDI-06)

(We also have seminars and trainings that take place, where we re-echo the lessons learned from SPED teachers' seminars and share it with us.)

Conclusions

In conclusion, this case study on the teaching strategies of teachers teaching students with special educational needs, particularly those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), has shed light on the importance of tailored approaches and inclusive practices. Through careful observation and analysis, it is evident that effective teaching strategies for students with ASD require a combination of individualized instruction, supportive learning environments, and a focus on communication and social skills development. The dedication and commitment of teachers in implementing these strategies have proven to be instrumental in promoting the academic and social growth of students with ASD.

After analyzing this case study, we can suggest some improvements to the teaching strategies teachers use for students with special educational needs, particularly those with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). First and foremost, it is essential for teachers to actively participate in continuous professional development and training to remain up-to-date with evidence-based practices and the latest research in teaching students with ASD. This will ensure that they have the necessary knowledge and skills to provide effective instruction.

Additionally, working closely with parents, specialists, and support staff is crucial in creating personalized education plans (IEPs) that cater to the unique needs, strengths, and areas of growth for every student with ASD. These personalized plans will allow for a customized approach to their education. It is crucial to establish a supportive and inclusive learning environment that fosters acceptance, understanding, and empathy among all students. One way to achieve this is by encouraging students to interact with their peers, creating classrooms that are sensory-friendly, and making sure that necessary accommodations and modifications are in place. Promoting collaboration and communication among teachers, specialists, and support staff is an important suggestion. Regular meetings and open lines of communication help in sharing strategies, resources, and progress monitoring.

Lastly, it would be highly beneficial to promote further research in teaching strategies for students with ASD and other special educational needs, beyond just focusing on Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). This broader research approach would contribute to a deeper understanding and the enhancement of instructional practices. By implementing these recommendations, educators can greatly enhance their teaching strategies and provide exceptional learning experiences for students with special educational needs. Additionally, fostering a culture of continuous improvement through ongoing research will ensure that teaching practices remain up-to-date and effective in meeting the diverse needs of students with special educational needs.

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